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FOREWORD

Dear friends and colleagues,

On behalf of the International Scientific Committee and the Local Organizing Committee, we are delighted to welcome you to Granada a new edition of the International Symposium on Thermodynamics of Metal Complexes (ISMEC 2025).

ISMEC 2025 will be the 53rd edition of a series of scientific meetings that begun in Parma in 1973, as the annual meeting of the *Italian Gruppo di Termodinamica dei Complessi* and later developed into a congress of international scope. Each year, researchers from all around the world come together to share their latest findings, foster collaboration, and promote the advancement of knowledge in the field of thermodynamics of metal complexes.

ISMEC 2025 is proud to continue with this tradition by offering a scientific program that highlights the most recent advances in the thermodynamics and kinetics of coordination processes. Our symposium will explore a wide range of topics including analytical, biomedical, environmental, inorganic, and physical chemistry. Main topics include:

- Complexation thermodynamics and kinetics
- Solution equilibria and coordination chemistry
- Complexation processes in supramolecular chemistry
- Metal-based reactivity and catalysis
- Metal-complex interactions with biomolecules
- Metals in diseases: transport, homeostasis, and toxicity
- Metal-based drugs: diagnosis and therapy
- Metal complexes of environmental and biological interests
- Nanostructured metal complexes
- Analytical methods and sensors based on complexation equilibria
- Computer methods for equilibrium analysis

These topics not only underscore the diversity and depth of the chemistry of metal complexes, but also reflect the innovative research being conducted by our community. As usual, the conference aims to provide a valuable discussion forum on recent advances on the above-mentioned areas, fostering new collaborations among researchers with complementary skills. In this context, ISMEC 2025 will feature a series of Plenary and Keynote lectures, as well as oral presentations and poster session, providing ample opportunities for participants to present their research and exchange ideas.

We are confident that ISMEC 2025 will be a stimulating and rewarding experience for all attendees. We encourage you to engage fully with the program, take advantage of the networking opportunities and enjoy the beautiful and vibrant city of Granada.

Welcome to ISMEC 2025! We are looking forward to sharing a fruitful and inspiring conference!

Sincerely,

Alicia Domínguez-Martín

Chair of the Organizing Committee of ISMEC 2025

Montserrat López-Mesas

President of the ISMEC Group

Granada, June 2025

Scientific Program

	9 th June	10 th June	11 th June	12 th June	
09:00-10:00		PL-2	PL-3	PL-4	
10:00-10:15		OC-5	OC-17	OC-28	
10:15-10:30		OC-6	OC-18	<i>Awards ceremony</i> OC- 29 Pulidori OC-30 Del Río	
10:30-10:45		OC-7	OC-19		
10:45-11:00		OC-8	OC-20		
11:00-11:30		Coffee Break	Coffee Break	Coffee Break	
11:30-12:00			KN-1	KN-3	KN-5
12:00-12:15		Registration	OC-9	OC-21	OC-31
12:15-12:30	OC-10		OC-22	OC-32	
12:30-12:45	OC-11		OC-23	OC-33	
12:45-13:00	OC-12		OC-24	OC-34	
13:00-13:15	OC-13		OC-25	OC-35	
13:15-15:30		Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	
15:30-15:45	Registration	KN-2	KN-4	OC-36	
15:45-16:00				OC-37	
16:00-16:15		OC-14	OC-26	OC-38	
16:15-16:30		OC-15	OC-27	Presentation "Emerging Analytical Techniques for Chemical Speciation Studies"	
16:30-16:45	Opening Ceremony	OC-16	ISMEC Group	Best Poster and Oral Awards Presentation ISMEC 2026	
16:45-17:00		Coffee Break			
17:00-17:15	PL-1	Poster Session	Free Time	Closing Ceremony	
17:15-17:30					
17:30-17:45					
17:45-18:00					
18:00-18:15				OC-1	
18:15-18:30	OC-2				
18:30-18:45	OC-3				
18:45-19:00	OC-4				
19:00-20:00	Welcome Reception			Gala Dinner	
20:00					

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

12:00 – 13:15 Registration

15:30 – 16:30 Registration

16:30-17:00 Opening Ceremony

Manuel Pérez Mendoza. Dean of the Faculty of Sciences, UGR

Montserrat López-Mesas. President of Group ISMEC

Antonio Cuenca Molina. Director Manager of Cámara Iberoamericana de España

Alicia Domínguez-Martín. Chair of ISMEC2025

Chairperson: Alicia Domínguez-Martín

17:00-18:00 Plenary Lecture 1: “Bioinorganic Perspectives on Metallophores: Unlocking New Strategies Against Antimicrobial Resistance”

Henryk Kozłowski. Faculty of Chemistry, University of Wrocław, Poland.

Chairperson: Enrique García-España

18:00-19:00 Oral Communications:

OC-01: “Antimicrobial actions of zinc oxide microcrystals: from design... to ‘ziotape’”

Claudia Pellerito. Department of Physics and Chemistry-Emilio Segrè, University of Palermo, Italy.

OC-02: “The hydrolytic stability of the human tubulin α 1A protein fragment – a potential reason for the role of metal ions in the development of neurodegenerative diseases”

Balázs Sándor. Department of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry, University of Debrecen, Hungary.

OC-03: “Metal-induced amide deprotonation and binding of model peptides to Cu(II), Zn(II) and Fe(II) metal ions”

Silvia Leveraro. Department of Chemical, Pharmaceutical and Agricultural Sciences, University of Ferrara, Italy.

OC-04: “Elucidating coordination chemistry of the peptidic models of putative Fe(II)-binding sites in bacterial transporter FeoB”

Bartosz Orzel. Faculty of Chemistry, University of Wrocław, Poland.

19:00-20:30 Welcome Reception

10 JUNE 2025

Chairperson: Andrea Melchior

09:00-10:00 Plenary Lecture 2: “Metal complexes for biomedical imaging”

Eva Jakab Toth. Centre of Molecular Biophysics, CNRS, Orléans, France.

Chairperson: Manuel Valiente

10:00-11:00 Oral Communications:

OC-05: “Tailoring Synthetic Siderophores for Precision Pathogen Targeting and Molecular Imaging Applications”.

Elżbieta Gumienna-Kontecka. University of Wrocław, Wrocław, Poland.

OC-06: “PEG-grafted Metal-organic Frameworks for Imaging: The key parameters for robust synthesis of stable nano-formulations”.

Maria Amparo Lopo-March. University of Valencia, Institute of Molecular Science, Paterna, Spain.

OC-07: “DACH-based hexadentate ligands for Pb²⁺ complexation: towards applications in nuclear medicine”.

Jennifer Storchl. Department of Chemical and Geological Sciences, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Modena, Italy.

OC-08: “Influence of Ligand Topology on the Physicochemical Parameters of Rare-Earth Metal Complexes of OCTAPA Derivatives”.

Balázs Szilágyi. Department of Physical Chemistry, University of Debrecen, Hungary.

11:00-11:30

Coffee Break

Chairperson: Demetrio Milea

11:30-12:00 Keynote 1: “Metal ions in ionic liquids: from fundamental studies to applications”

Andrea Melchior. Polytechnic Department, Chemical Technologies Laboratories, University of Udine, Italy.

Chairperson: Sofia Gama

12:00-13:15 Oral Communications:

OC-09: “Ferrocene-containing ionic liquids as catalysts of ring-opening polymerization”.

Jan Honziček. Institute of Chemistry and Technology of Macromolecular Materials, University of Pardubice, Czech Republic.

OC-10: “From Solution Equilibria to Photocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution: Exploiting Thermodynamics Concepts in Contemporary Catalysis”.

Matteo Savastano. Department for the Promotion of Human Science and Quality of Life, University San Raffaele Roma, Italy.

OC-11: ““Heme vs. Cobalamin, Iron vs. Cobalt – and Beyond: Rationalization of Differing Reactivity in Redox and Coordination”.

Radu Silaghi-Dumitrescu. Babes-Bolyai University, Cluj, Romania.

OC-12: “Tailoring antioxidant activities: Metal-type dependent, highly efficient SOD or catalase mimetics”.

Álvaro Martínez-Camarena. Departament de Química Inorgànica, Universitat de València, Paterna, Spain.

OC-13: “From enantiomeric exchange to antimicrobial activity: the enzymatic secrets of salivary peptides”.

Anna Ślusarczyk. Faculty of Chemistry, University of Wrocław, Poland.

13:15-15:30

Lunch Break

Chairperson: Magdalena Rowinska-Zyrek

15:30-16:00 Keynote 2: “Multi-scale and multimodal imaging of trace elements combining NanoSIMS and Synchrotron techniques”

Iris H. Valido. Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain.

Chairperson: Michel Meyer

16:00-16:45 Oral Communications:

OC-14: “Formation, decomplexation and isomerisation mechanisms of lanthanide (III) complexes of 18-py₂N₄Ac₄ (H₄pyta): a large macrocycle for large metal ions.”.

Petr Hermann. Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Univerzita Karlova, Czech Republic.

OC-15: “Structural diversity in zinc(II) complexes with substituted adamantane-1-carbonyl-N-hydrazinecarbothioamides”.

Natalia Álvarez. Química Inorgánica, Departamento Estrella Campos, Universidad de la República, Montevideo, Uruguay.

OC-16: “Self-Assembly Interactions of pyridyl functionalised btp ligands with *d*- and *f*-metals”.

Niamh Anne O’Shea. Trinity Biomedical Science Institution, Trinity College Dublin, Ireland.

16:45-17:15 Coffee Break

17:15-19:00 Poster Session

11 JUNE 2025

Chairperson: Tarita Biver

09:00-10:00 Plenary Lecture 3: “Uranium: Its Theoretical and Experimental Speciation from Mining Operations to the Environment”

Pascal Reiller. Atomic Energy and Alternative Energies Commission | CEA · Département de Physico-Chimie, France.

Chairperson: Vieri Fusi

10:00-11:00 Oral Communications:

OC-17: “Bioaccumulation and speciation of Cobalt in *Mytilus galloprovincialis*: insights into metal-biomolecule interactions in a marine sentinel organism”.

María Rosa Beccia. Université Côte d’Azur, CNRS, Institut de Chimie de Nice, France.

OC-18: “Recovery of neodymium and praseodymium from waste magnet via solid phase extraction with natural zeolite”.

José Alejandro Ricardo García., Dipartimento Politecnico, Università di Udine, Chemical Technologies Laboratories, Italy.

OC-19: “Environmental applications of biologically active transition metal complexes”.

Giampaolo Barone. Dipartimento di Scienze e Tecnologie Biologiche, Chimiche e Farmaceutiche, Università degli Studi di Palermo, Italy.

OC-20: “Complexation and Precipitation Equilibria in the Cadmium(II) – Nicotinic Acid System. A Potentiometric, Spectrophotometric and ^{113}Cd - NMR study”.

Anna Sofia Sammarco. Department of Chemistry and Biology, University of Salerno, Fisciano (SA), Italy.

11:00-11:30 Coffee Break

Chairperson: Miguel Ángel Galindo Cuesta

11:30-12:00 Keynote 3: “Structural and optical properties of DNA-stabilized silver nanoclusters”

Tom Vosch. Department of Chemistry, University of Copenhagen, Denmark.

Chairperson: Raffaella Biesuz

12:00-13:15 Oral Communications:

OC-21: “How reliable is the evaluation of DNA binding constants? Insights and best practices based on an inter-laboratory fluorescence titration study”.

Tarita Biver. Department of Chemistry and Industrial Chemistry, University of Pisa, Italy.

OC-22: “Ni(II) Cylinder Preferentially Binds DNA Three-way Junctions Blocking DNA synthesis and Triggers DNA Damage in Cancer Cells”.

Jaroslav Malina. Czech Academy of Sciences, Institute of Biophysics, Czech Republic.

OC-23: “Syntheses and metal ion binding strengths of novel ambidentate ligands to construct anticancer drug candidates with hypoxia activation”.

Péter Buglyó. Department of Inorganic & Analytical Chemistry, University of Debrecen, Debrecen, Hungary.

OC-24: “Novel ruthenium (II) polypyridyl complexes: synthesis, interaction with mitochondrial G-Quadruplexes and biological activity in HCT116 human colorectal cancer cells”.

Laura Marretta. University of Palermo, Department of Biological, Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technologies, Palermo, Italy

OC-25: “Silver-binding to DNA containing 7-deazapurine nucleobases”.

Antonio Pérez-Romero. Departamento de Química Inorgánica. University of Granada, Spain.

13:15-15:30 Lunch Break

Chairperson: Juan Niclós-Gutiérrez

15:30-16:00 Keynote 4: “Thermodynamic insights into metal complexes with kojic acid-based ligands: a journey through key results and evolving perspectives”

Rosita Cappai. Department of Chemical, Physical, Mathematical and Natural Sciences, Sassari, Italy.

16:00-16:30 Oral Communications:

OC-26: “From scratch to speciation: exploring the aqueous coordination chemistry of 2-(aminomethyl)-quinolin-8-ol”.

Matteo Marafante. Dipartimento di Chimica, Università di Torino, Italy

OC-27: “Host-guest complexes in aqueous solution: insights on the molecular recognition properties of carboxylato-prism[*n*]arene containers”.

Giuseppina D. G. Santonoceta, Department of Chemical Sciences, University of Catania, Viale A. Doria 6, 95125 Catania, Italy.

16:30-17:30 ISMEC Group Meeting

12 JUNE 2025

Chairperson: Marilena Tolazzi

09:00-10:00 Plenary Lecture 4: “Anticancer drugs based on metal complexes of 2-imine-8-hydroxyquinolines”

Isabel Correia. Centro de Química Estrutural and Departamento de Engenharia Química, Institute of Molecular Sciences, Instituto Superior Técnico, Lisboa, Portugal.

10:00-10:15 Oral Communications:

OC-28: “Metal Ions And Peptides – A Bioinorganic Symphony or Antimicrobial Action”.

Magdalena Rowińska-Żyrek. Faculty of Chemistry, University of Wrocław, Wrocław, Poland.

Chairperson: Alicia Domínguez-Martín

10:15-11:00 Pulidori & Del Río Awards ceremony:

Introduction: Maurizio Remelli

OC-29 Fernando Pulidori Award: “Master Survival Strategy: Asp2 zincophore and ZrfC transporter on the front line in the battle for the host's Zn(II)”.

Kinga Garstka-Litwin. Faculty of Chemistry, University of Wrocław, Poland

Introduction: Antonio Cuenca Molina

OC-30 Andrés M. Del Río Award: “Solar-thermal energy release in a water-soluble push-pull norbornadiene-derivative triggered by a Co(II)-porphyrin complex”.

Franco Castro. Área Química Inorgánica, Departamento Estrella Campos, Facultad de Química, Universidad de la República, Montevideo, Uruguay.

11:00-11:30 Coffee Break

Chairperson: Antonio Bianchi

11:30-12:00 Keynote 5: “Enhancing the anti-oxidant power of Superoxide Dismutase and Catalase mimics”

Salvador Blasco. Departamento de Química Inorgánica, Instituto de Ciencia Molecular. Universidad de Valencia, Spain.

Chairperson: Maria Rosa Beccia

12:00-13:15 Oral Communications:

OC-31: “Electrochemical synthesis of cluster helicates with biomedical potential”.

Sandra Fernández-Fariña. Departamento de Química Inorgánica, Facultad de Química, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Spain.

OC-32: “Peptide Inhibitors of Metalloproteinases: Structural Insights into Complexes with Zinc and the Catalytic Domain”.

Sławomir Potocki, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Wrocław, Poland.

OC-33: “Comparing the Bioinorganic Chemistry of MUC7 Fragment and Its Peptidomimetics: Distinct or Similar?”.

Klaudia Szarszoń. Faculty of Chemistry, University of Wrocław, Poland

OC-34: “Peptide-Based Inhibitors Targeting MMP for Cancer Suppression: Thermodynamic and Structural Insights into Zn(II)-MMP-Inhibitor Ternary Complexes.”.

Paulina Potok. Faculty of Chemistry, University of Wrocław, Wrocław, Poland.

OC-35: “Exploiting Knowledge from Solution Chemistry to Search for Research Funding”.

Manuel Valiente. Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. Departament de Química. Centre GTS, Spain.

13:15-15:30 Lunch Break

Chairperson: Petr Hermann

15:30-16:15 Oral Communications:

OC-36: “PyES 2.0 – a solution to optimize stability constants from potentiometric data with unique features”.

Silvia Berto. Dipartimento di Chimica, Università di Torino, Torino, Italy.

OC-37: “Potentiometric investigation of solution equilibria in the Sn^{2+} - H_2O - F^- system using Glass membrane, Fluoride Ion-Selective and Sn(Hg) amalgam electrodes”.

Mariacristina Bianco. Department of Chemistry and Biology, University of Salerno, Fisciano (SA), Italy

OC-38: “Dirhenium(III) clusters of biological interests”.

Nataliia Shtemenko. Instituto de Ciencia Molecular (ICMOL), Universitat de València, Paterna, Spain.

16:15-16:30 Presentation “Emerging Analytical Techniques for Chemical Speciation Studies”

Chairperson: Alicia Domínguez-Martín

16:30-16:45 Best Poster and Best Oral Young Researchers Awards

16:45-17:00 Presentation ISMEC 2026

17:00 Closing Ceremony

Tarita Biver. Elected President of Group ISMEC

Alicia Domínguez-Martín. Chair of ISMEC2025

20:00

Gala Dinner “La Chumbera” Restaurant

Address: Camino del Sacromonte 107, 18010 Granada

Plenary Lectures

Bioinorganic Perspectives on Metallophores: Unlocking New Strategies Against Antimicrobial Resistance

**Henryk KOZŁOWSKI,^{a)} Daniela VALENSIN,^{b)} Elżbieta GUMIENNA-KONTECKA,^{a)}
Kinga GARSTKA-LITWIN,^{a)} Magdalena ROWIŃSKA-ŻYREK,^{a)} Aleskandra
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The growing threat of antimicrobial resistance underscores the urgent need for novel therapeutic strategies targeting pathogen-specific processes. We unravel the molecular mechanisms underlying metal ion transport in pathogens and to exploit these insights for enhancing host nutritional immunity. Focusing on Fe(III), Cu(II), Zn(II), and Ni(II) ions, we conducted comprehensive thermodynamic, structural, and microbiological studies of metallophore-metal complexes and their interactions with transporter proteins, characterizing the metal-binding properties of natural and biomimetic metallophores, revealing key factors that determine their stability, selectivity, and efficiency. [1-3] Our studies showed that specific metallophores form exceptionally stable complexes with their target metal ions, often outcompeting host molecules involved in metal sequestration.

Moreover, we identified distinct interaction patterns between metallophore-metal complexes and microbial transporters, uncovering new molecular signatures crucial for selective recognition. Microbiological validation confirmed that interfering with metallophore-mediated metal uptake can impair pathogen growth and virulence.[4] These findings highlight metal transport as a highly promising, underexploited target for antimicrobial strategies and pave the way for the development of pathogen-specific imaging and therapeutic tools, offering new hope in the fight against antimicrobial resistance.[5]

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- [1] K. Garstka, A. Hecel, H. Kozłowski, M. Rowińska-Żyrek, *Metallomics*, **2022**, 14, mfac042
- [3] K. Garstka, D. Bellotti, J. Wąty, H. Kozłowski M. Remelli, M. Rowińska-Żyrek, *Dalton Transactions*, **2023**, 52, 16140-16150
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- [4] A. Mular, K. Piasta, A. Jedyńczuk, K. Kamińska, E. Olshvang, N. Metzler Nolte, E. Wojaczyńska, H. Kozłowski, E. Gumienna-Kontecka, *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, **2024**, 501, 215551/1-215551/40
- [5] K. Garstka, A. Hecel, H. Kozłowski, A. Domínguez-Martín, K. Szewczyk, M. Rowińska-Żyrek, *Dalton Transactions*, **2025**, 1-12.

Metal complexes for biomedical imaging

Eva JAKAB TOTH

Centre of Molecular Biophysics, CNRS, rue Charles Sadron, 45071 Orléans, France

Metal complexes are widely used as imaging probes in various imaging modalities. One important field in molecular imaging involves the detection of physico-chemical parameters of tissues, concentration of ions, metabolites, etc. by applying smart, activatable imaging probes that are responsive to the specific parameter. Magnetic Resonance Imaging is well adapted to the design of responsive probes. The efficacy (relaxivity) of the probe has to be selectively influenced, based on coordination chemistry concepts, by the biomarker that we wish to detect. We have been developing potential smart contrast agents to detect cation or neurotransmitter concentration changes, or to monitor redox state and enzyme activity [1].

Following recent toxicity concerns related to the use of Gd^{3+} complexes in MRI, there is an active research for more biocompatible alternatives. Among these, Mn^{2+} chelates have great promise. However, the lower charge and the lack of ligand-field stabilization energy for Mn^{2+} are not favorable to achieve high thermodynamic stability, and the highly labile nature of Mn^{2+} sets an even more difficult challenge to meet. We have recently demonstrated that rigid and pre-organized bispidine ligand structures are particularly interesting in this respect [2].

We also explore the potential of fluorine-containing small Mn^{2+} or Fe^{3+} chelates as alternatives to perfluorinated nanoparticles in ^{19}F MRI. In chelates where several magnetically equivalent ^{19}F atoms are placed at an appropriate distance from the metal center, these paramagnetic ions generate maximized relaxation effects which can be efficiently harvested by using ultrafast acquisition sequences. The redox properties of these metal ions can be further exploited to design redox responsive ^{19}F MRI agents [3]. In this talk, representative examples from these fields will be discussed.

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- [1] (a) F. Oukhatar, S. Mème, W. Mème, F. Szeremeta, N. K. Logothetis, G. Angelovski, and É. Tóth, *ACS Chem. Neuroscience*, **2015**, 6, 219. (b) R. Jouclas, S. Laine, S. V. Eliseeva, J. Mandel, F. Szeremeta, P. Retailleau, J. He, J.-F. Gallard, A. Pallier, C. S. Bonnet, S. Petoud, P. Durand, É. Tóth, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2024**, 63, e202317728.
- [2] (a) D. Ndiaye, M. Sy, A. Pallier, S. Mème, I. de Silva, S. Lacerda, A. M. Nonat, L. J. Charbonnière and É. Tóth, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2020**, 59, 11958. (b) P. Cieslik, P. Comba, B. Dittmar, D. Ndiaye, É. Tóth, G. Velmurugan, H. Wadepohl, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2022**, 61, e202115580, (c) D. Ndiaye, P. Cieslik, H. Wadepohl, A. Pallier, S. Mème, P. Comba, É. Tóth *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2022**, 144, 22212. (d) D. Ndiaye, M. Sy, W. Thor, L. J. Charbonnière, A. M. Nonat, É. Tóth *Chem. Eur. J.* **2023**, 29, e202301880
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Uranium: Its Theoretical and Experimental Speciation from Mining Operations to the Environment

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Since its discovery by Martin Klaproth in 1789 [1], who named this new element from the recently discovered planet Uranus, and metallic form, isolated by Eugène Périgot in 1841 [2], uranium has been the center of a large body of works. Uranium is a relatively abundant element on Earth. Even if radioactive the period of ^{238}U ($4.5 \cdot 10^9$ years) implies that it is still strongly present in Earth crust. It seems to participate to the thermic energy of the Earth core. Uranium has a rich chemistry, including 4 redox states, and is forming compounds with the majority of the elements. This element is at the center place of the electricity production using nuclear reactor.

Edmond Becquerel [3,4], using a rotoscope, evidenced the green luminescence of uranium salts, which we know now being in its +VI redox state. Becquerel has remarked that the luminescence bands were characteristic of the type of salts he was observing. Some 30 years later, Henri Becquerel [5], Edmond's son, remarked that uranium salts were impressing photographic plates even in the dark, discovering radioactivity.

After Edmond Becquerel, and since the advent of pulsed lasers, the luminescence of uranium(VI) has allowed to acquire thermodynamic data, structural and speciation information. Particularly, the formation of sulphatouranyl (VI) ($\text{UO}_2(\text{SO}_4)_n^{2-2n}$) [6-8] and alkaline earth(II) triscarbonatouranyl(VI) complexes ($\text{Ae}_n\text{UO}_2(\text{CO}_3)_3^{(4-2n)-}$) [9-13]. The former complexes are forming during sulfuric acid treatment of the uranium ores during and after mining operations [14]. The latter were first evidenced in a seepage water from a uranium mine tailing pile [9], even if solids were known since the 19th century [15]. These latter complexes, particularly with calcium and magnesium, have been shown to be dominant in weakly alkaline and carbonated waters, including seawater [16], and even in deep underground groundwaters [17]. Since 1996, the influence of the $\text{Ae}_n\text{UO}_2(\text{CO}_3)_3^{(4-2n)-}$ complexes was revealed on uranium(VI) adsorption on minerals [18,19] and on kinetics of uranium(VI) reduction by bacteria [20].

In our laboratory the clarification of the thermodynamic data of both the $\text{UO}_2(\text{SO}_4)_n^{2-2n}$ and $\text{Ae}_n\text{UO}_2(\text{CO}_3)_3^{(4-2n)-}$ complexes have been done using two different techniques: time-resolved laser-induced fluorescence spectroscopy (TRLIFS) [8,10-13], and capillary electrophoresis coupled to inductively coupled plasma spectrometry (CE-ICP-MS) [21]. The thermodynamic constants and specific ion interaction parameters, are coherent and allow the description the speciation at varying ionic strength and ascertaining the calculation of speciation in natural environment [22].

As an application, and in collaboration with the French uranium mining operative ORANO, we had the opportunity to monitor the speciation of uranium (VI) in different mining context. First, we spectroscopically evidenced the presence of $\text{Ca}_n\text{UO}_2(\text{CO}_3)_3^{(4-2n)-}$ complexes at a treatment step in the site of le Bosc (Lodève, France) [17], which was in agreement with the speciation

calculation using thermodynamic constants. Second, we also evidenced the presence of $\text{Ca}_n\text{UO}_2(\text{CO}_3)_3^{(4-2n)-}$ complexes in effluents from a uranium sandstone mine (Niger) [23]. Finally, we were able to monitor, both using thermodynamic calculation and TRLIFS, the evolution from $\text{UO}_2(\text{SO}_4)_n^{2-2n}$ to $\text{Ca}_n\text{UO}_2(\text{CO}_3)_3^{(4-2n)-}$ during the treatment of acidic waters coming out of mining piles before the outlet to the nearby river in the le Cellier legacy-mine (France), conforming to regulations [24].

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Anticancer drugs based on metal complexes of 2-imine-8-hydroxyquinolines

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Cancer treatment remains a significant global challenge, requiring, more than ever, the development of therapeutic agents that are not only effective but also highly selective to minimize off-target toxicity. Metal complexes of 8-hydroxyquinoline (8HQ) have demonstrated promising anticancer potential, largely due to 8HQ's strong metal-chelating ability, chemical stability, and a broad-spectrum of bioactivity. When coordinated to biologically active metal ions, such as Zn, Cu, V, Ni, Fe, and Ru, these complexes can exhibit synergistic or additive therapeutic effects, enhancing their overall pharmacological profile.

This work highlights the recent advances made by our research group in the synthesis, structural characterization, and biological evaluation of 8HQ-derived metal complexes. Our research focused on novel 8HQ ligands modified at position 2 with imine functionalities (Fig. 1), aiming to modulate both coordination behavior and biological activity. Special attention was given to overcoming challenges related to poor selectivity and limited aqueous solubility - two major obstacles in the clinical translation of metal-based drugs.

Figure 1 – Families of 8-hydroxyquinoline ligands developed in our group.

In vitro anticancer activity was screened against a panel of aggressive cancer cell lines, including malignant melanoma, colon, lung, and triple-negative breast cancer. The results revealed potent cytotoxic effects, with mechanistic studies indicating that the compounds exert their anticancer activity primarily through reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation, leading to oxidative stress and apoptotic cell death.

To address the *in vivo* limitations posed by non-selective toxicity and poor solubility, a nanoliposomal drug delivery strategy was employed. This encapsulation approach facilitated passive targeting via the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect, thereby improving tumor selectivity and bioavailability.

Overall, our findings [1-6] underscore the therapeutic potential of 8HQ-based metal complexes as promising candidates for anticancer drug development, paving the way for further preclinical investigations and formulation strategies to optimize their clinical utility.

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Keynote Lectures

Metal ions in ionic liquids: from fundamental studies to applications

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Ionic liquids (ILs) are salts composed by organic cations and organic/inorganic anions (Figure 1), which are in the liquid state for temperatures below 100 °C. Among them, room temperature ILs (RTILs) are liquids at ~25 °C. Such low melting points originate from the large size of the ions and strong charge delocalization which causes a damping of the coulombic interaction, thus decreasing the lattice energy of the salt [1]. Several useful properties characterize ionic liquids: negligible volatility, non-flammability, high thermal and electrochemical stabilities, high conductivities, hydrophobicity, and good solvation ability for both neutral and charged species [2]. Owing to these peculiar properties, ILs have been proposed for numerous applications in the last two decades: electrolytes for energy storage (batteries), solvents for catalysis, electrodepositions, chemical separations and analysis, corrosion protection and pharmaceutical research [2].

Numerous of the above-mentioned applications involve the presence of dissolved metal ions and/or metal complexes. For instance, their wide electrochemical windows coupled with high electrochemical and thermal stabilities can provide RTILs that could be considered as ideal electrolytes for batteries [3]. RTILs have emerged and attracted increasing interest in the past few years as "green" substitutes of volatile organic solvents in hydrometallurgical recovery processes of critical raw materials (CRM) deriving from mining activity or end-of-life devices[4]. In this field, the recycling of critical raw materias assumed a growing importance due to the increasing demand related to its use in strategic technologies, such as Li-ion batteries or motors for electric mobility [5].

Speciation of the metal ions in the IL phase, and thus the knowledge of the type, stability and structure of the species formed are essential pieces of information for the rational design and understanding of separation processes.

In this contribution, a selection of recent studies on coordination and solvation properties of several metal ions (Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ag^+ ...) in some common RTILs based on $[\text{C}_n\text{mim}]^+$ (1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium) and $[\text{P}_{\text{nnnn}}]^+$ (tetraalkylphosphonium) cations is presented. By combining spectroscopic (UV-Vis, FTIR, XAS) and thermodynamic (ITC) techniques it is possible to obtain reliable models describing the nature of the solvated metal ions and the species formed with the most common anions (e.g. chloride or nitrate). Experimental data are succesfully complemented by ab initio calculations and molecular dynamics simulations which demonstrate to be powerful tools to provide information on the structural properties of the

solvates and complexes, as well as on the IL organization beyond the first solvation sphere of the metal ion.

In the context of separation applications, the contribution focuses on the extraction of two CRMs, cobalt and rare earth elements (REEs), from aqueous solutions. The use of room-temperature ionic liquids (RTILs) in the liquid-liquid extraction of these CRMs presents a promising and sustainable approach, offering advantages such as low energy requirements, high selectivity, and ease of implementation. Some recent results on the application of tetraalkylphosphonium RTILs in for the recovery of Co and REEs will be presented.

Figure 1. Structures of some common ionic components of ionic liquids

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Multi-scale and multimodal imaging of trace elements combining NanoSIMS and Synchrotron techniques

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Multi-scale and multimodal imaging techniques have transformed the study of trace elements in environmental and biological samples, providing unprecedented insights into their structure, composition, and functionality. This work combines NanoSIMS with synchrotron radiation techniques (μ XRF, and μ XAS) applied to two different samples, yielding key information in these research areas:

- 1) Zinc deficiency is a global public health concern. Zinc-enriched yeast (ZnYeast) is a promising biological source with Zn-integrated structures. Safety evaluations by EFSA require comprehensive data on bioavailability and clarification of its Zn species. NanoSIMS examined subcellular Zn distribution in *Saccharomyces* strains, while μ XAS evaluated the speciation, which is crucial for understanding Zn homeostasis and future legal evaluations of ZnYeast as an organic zinc supplement.
- 2) Sargassum algae influx onto Caribbean beaches poses ecological and economic threats, with tons of algae washing ashore annually, containing pollutants like arsenic. Proper disposal is crucial to prevent arsenic leaching during degradation. NanoSIMS revealed arsenic localization in algae cells, while μ XRF and μ XAS determined arsenic speciation, providing vital insights for Sargassum algae treatment strategies.

The study showcases the effectiveness of combining NanoSIMS with synchrotron radiation techniques (μ XRF, and μ XAS) for analyzing environmental and biological samples, highlighting the significant potential of these imaging techniques in solving complex research problems.

Structural and optical properties of DNA-stabilized silver nanoclusters

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In the past twenty years, DNA has been used as a scaffold to stabilize atomically monodisperse silver nanoclusters. Due to the limited number of atoms that make up the cluster, DNA-embedded Ag nanoclusters (DNA-AgNCs) are characterized by discrete energy levels, hence they can absorb and emit visible and near-infrared (NIR) light. The combination of mass spectrometry and single crystal X-ray diffraction of HPLC-purified DNA-AgNCs is a powerful tool to determine the charge and structure of the encapsulated AgNC. In this talk, I will give an overview of photophysical properties and structural aspects of DNA-AgNCs. More information can be found in the references listed below [1-5].

Figure 1. A) Polycrystals of DNA₂-(Ag₁₆Cl₂)⁸⁺, and B) related structure. This cluster is formed by 16 silvers (gray), 2 chlorido ligands (green) and two 10-mer DNA strands. C) Polycrystals of DNA₂-(Ag₂₈Cl₂)¹⁴⁺, and D) corresponding structure. This cluster is formed by 28 silvers (gray), 2 chlorido ligands (green) and two 16-mer DNA strands.

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Thermodynamic insights into metal complexes with kojic acid-based ligands: a journey through key results and evolving perspectives

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Understanding the solution thermodynamics of metal–ligand interactions is a key point in the design of metal complexes with tailored properties under well-defined biological and environmental conditions. Kojic acid (5-hydroxy-2-(hydroxymethyl)-4-pyrone, KA), known for its antibiotic, antifungal, and tyrosinase-inhibitory properties, has also emerged as a versatile building block in the design of multidentate ligands. The functionalization of the pyrone ring at position 2 or 6 allows the synthesis of bis- and tris-KA derivatives through efficient and low-cost strategies. The use of linkers with varying length and chemical nature enables the modulation of chelating properties, affording ligands capable of binding metal ions such as Fe³⁺, Al³⁺, Ga³⁺, Zn²⁺, Cu²⁺, V⁴⁺, Cd²⁺, and Pb²⁺, and influencing their *in vivo* sequestering potential [1-4]. A multi-technique approach, involving potentiometry, UV-visible spectrophotometry, NMR spectroscopy, and quantum mechanical calculations, has been employed to characterize the solution equilibria and gain insights into the coordination modes. The comparative analysis reveals how subtle changes in the ligand architecture significantly influence metal ion binding, complex stoichiometry, and overall stability. Particular emphasis is placed on the relationship between ligand structure and the thermodynamic parameters governing complex formation. Overall, this is a contribution to the broader understanding of structure–stability relationships in coordination chemistry and provides useful design principles for the development of functional chelating agents with potential applications in environmental remediation, metal sensing, and medicinal chemistry.

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Enhancing the anti-oxidant power of Superoxide Dismutase and Catalase mimics.

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Anti-oxidants are essential in regulating many chemical processes in living organisms where free radicals and other reactive species may be produced. Several diseases and pathologies are directly or indirectly linked to imbalances or malfunction of these anti-oxidant agents of the body. Enzymes such as Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT) are critical for maintaining the reactive oxygen species (ROS) concentration at non-toxic levels. Our research focuses on learning and imitating how these crucial enzymes work, and we aim to design small-molecule mimics of these enzymes to replicate their antioxidant activity for potential use in therapeutic applications related to control the oxidative damage caused by ROS.[1] This is no easy undertaking for there are many factors at play. Indeed, high activity, high stability compounds are desirable, but they must also prove to be non toxic, easy to manufacture and to deliver to the biological target.

Our initial approach in this endeavor was an imidazolate-bridged Cu(II) complex which is structurally similar to Cu₂Zn₂SOD active center.[2] This complex, although structurally promising, its SOD-like activity was only moderate. From this point on, better and improved compounds, featuring either Cu(II) or Mn(II) have been prepared, and reported. Some of them have SOD-like activity close to the native Cu₂Zn₂SOD enzyme.[3] In this talk we will discuss these developments and elaborate on new strategies and synthetic designs for the improvement of the anti-oxidant activity which are currently being applied. These include grafting active compounds onto nanoparticles, adding new functional groups and promoting the formation of vesicles or liposomes in order to improve activity and barrier crossing.[4]

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Oral Communications

**Antimicrobial actions of zinc oxide microcrystals:
from design... to ‘ziotape’**

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ZnO is a versatile material exhibiting reconfigurable morphologies and significant antibacterial activity towards gram positive and negative microorganisms, connected with their high surface to volume ratio and their physicochemical properties. Several models are suggested for explaining the mechanisms of bacterial growth inhibition for nanostructured ZnO, leveraging electrostatic interactions between ZnO and cell walls affecting bacterial cell integrity, release of antimicrobial Zn²⁺ ions, which is connected to accumulation of ZnO into bacteria cells and finally ROS formation [1]. However, ZnO nanoparticles are usually detrimental to cell viability, so new ZnO based synthetic strategies are needed to better control the ZnO biocidal effects.

To bridge this knowledge gap, in this work, we engineered a new synthetic approach based on the wet synthesis of ZnO to exploit experimental design allowing for improving synthesis yield (obtained at temperatures < 90 °C) [2], photocatalysis efficiency and the antibacterial properties of the microcrystals. The resulting ZnO-based microcrystals stabilized in a biocompatible amino-functionalized cellulose solid supports or microcrystalline matrices matrix allow for a prolonged (>24 hours) antibacterial activity based on dual mechanical/chemical routes. In the former, a direct disruptive mechanical interaction occurs with bacteria due to impaling with asymmetrical functionalized ZnO diffusing from the cellulose in presence of external stimuli (fuel or light) [3], that facilitate their motion and interaction with bacteria. For the latter, the zinc release in solution might modify the zinc homeostasis, leading to reactive oxygen species (ROS). Antimicrobial assays are carried out with two reference strains (*Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*) with different structural/physiological features, highlighting both the time and concentration dependency of ZnO microcrystals in killing bacteria.

Showing the technological relevance of the research, we also demonstrate the scalability of this approach towards antibacterial products dispersed in cellulose matrix and we present it as Ziotape, antimicrobial modulable ZnO-based adhesive patches to be applied on surfaces. These "smart" supports incorporate antibacterial properties that might allow to reduce the use of antimicrobials, disinfectants, drugs or creams. Currently we are carrying out experiments

trying to elucidate the antibacterial mechanisms of ZnO microcrystals: in fact, besides a direct disruptive mechanical interaction with bacteria due to ZnO particles diffusion from the cellulose in presence of external stimuli (fuel or light), also the zinc release in solution might be critical modifying the zinc homeostasis and leading to reactive oxygen species (ROS). Electrostatic interactions between ZnO microparticles and cell walls affecting bacterial cell integrity have been also described [4,5].

Figure. Antibacterial mechanisms of ZnO microcrystals

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The hydrolytic stability of the human tubulin α 1A protein fragment – a potential reason for the role of metal ions in the development of neurodegenerative diseases

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Alpha tubulin proteins are recognised as a key component in the process of cell division, due to their role in dimerisation and polymerisation, which results the formation of microtubules in eukaryotes, however in the context of Alzheimer's disease (AD) and other neurodegenerative diseases (NDD), it may also play an important role, as alterations in their structure and disintegration have been observed. The present study investigates the human tubulin α 1A protein fragment(s), in the presence of essential copper(II) and the toxic nickel(II) metal ions.

Figure 1. - Illustrated interactions between the microtubule and copper(II) and nickel(II) ions, as observed from the inside.

The aforementioned natural protein fragment contains the $-(S/T)XH-$ amino acid motif, which sequences were previously identified as the active sites of a metal-ion-induced, sequence-specific hydrolysis process. [1, 2, 3] The solution equilibrium studies (pH-potentiometry, UV-Vis- and CD spectroscopy) demonstrated that the nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes formed under the physiological pH conditions exhibit enhanced thermodynamic stability.

Figure 2. Analysis of the HPLC chromatograms as a function of time for systems consisting of $Ni(II):Ac-LTHTTL-NH_2$ 1:1 (a) and $Cu(II):Ac-LTHTTL-NH_2$ 1:1 (b) at 37 °C, pH=7.4 provided by 20 mM HEPES buffer.

The RP-HPLC and MS studies confirmed the irreversible behaviour of the ligand, due to the formation of the intermediate and final products of the hydrolytic reaction, which were induced by the nickel(II) and copper(II) metal ions. In the presence of nickel(II) ions under conditions of pH 8.2 and temperature 37 °C, the kinetic parameters of the reaction were determined. The half-life value for the formation of the intermediate product were found to be 3.70 hours, while for the formation of the final product was 73.75 hours.

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Metal-induced amide deprotonation and binding of model peptides to Cu(II), Zn(II) and Fe(II) metal ions

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The elucidation of metal-peptide interactions is an extremely important aspect of bioinorganic chemistry, also in the view of designing novel therapeutic agents. While Cu(II)/peptide coordination chemistry is extensively documented [1,2], the coordination behaviour of Zn(II) and Fe(II), particularly concerning the backbone amide deprotonation and binding, still remains controversial [3,4]. In fact, in the case of Cu(II) ions, histidine imidazole often acts as an anchoring site, at acidic pH and, increasing the alkalinity of the solution, the metal coordination might involve the backbone amides towards the N- and/or C-terminal directions. A similar behaviour is also possible, but not fully established, for Zn(II) and Fe(II) metal ions (Fig. 1) [5].

In the present investigation, we studied three model peptides protected at both terminal ends: Ac-AAAHAAA-NH₂, Ac-AAPHAAA-NH₂, Ac-AAPHPAA-NH₂. In the second peptide, an alanine has been substituted with a proline residue in position 3, while in the third peptide, a double substitution has been done in position 3 and 5. Proline is the only natural amino acids having a secondary amino nitrogen. The introduction of proline acts as a sort of “breaking point” in progressive coordination of metal ion to the backbone, since it does not contain replaceable amide protons, thus making the typical stepwise coordination of consecutive amide nitrogens impossible.

The thermodynamic and spectroscopic characterization of the formed metal complexes has been achieved by means of potentiometry, UV-Vis spectrophotometry, circular dichroism, electron paramagnetic resonance, calorimetric titrations, mass spectrometry and DFT calculations.

The results show distinct coordination behaviors for Zn(II) and Fe(II), compared to Cu(II). Both experimental and computational results agree that the metal-induced amide deprotonation and binding are not likely for the three model peptides in the case of both Zn(II) and Fe(II).

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Fig. 1 – Coordination hypotheses of backbone amide nitrogens to divalent metal ions.

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Elucidating coordination chemistry of the peptidic models of putative Fe(II)-binding sites in bacterial transporter FeoB

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The effective acquisition of metal ions is indispensable for bacterial survival and pathogenicity. During the infection, bacteria need to assimilate metal ions from the host. However, the host significantly reduces the free metal pool available to pathogens in a process called nutritional immunity. [1] Therefore, bacteria have developed a plethora of various strategies for the efficient uptake of crucial metals, such as Fe, which can be transported in both Fe(II) and Fe(III) forms. In anaerobic conditions, Fe(II) is the prevalent form of iron. For pathogenic bacteria occupying such anaerobic niches, e.g. parts of the mammalian digestive system, efficient Fe(II) uptake is crucial for survival. Despite its great significance, the mechanisms by which bacteria acquire ferrous iron are still poorly understood, especially at the molecular level.

Contrary to Fe(III), the good solubility of Fe(II) allows for its uptake as a free metal ion. In Gram-negative bacteria, ferrous iron is transported through the outer bacterial membrane by channels called porins, which most probably are not metal-specific. Then, Fe(II) is transported from the periplasm, across the inner membrane, to the cytoplasm of the bacterial cell, by more specific transmembrane proteins. The Feo system is considered the most important and most widespread in bacteria Fe(II) transport system, often crucial for bacterial pathogenicity, which underscores its significance. [2]

While Feo system can consist of three proteins, the most important is the transmembrane FeoB protein, which transports Fe(II) across the membrane (Fig.1). Despite its great significance, neither the mechanism of the transport nor the metal-binding regions have yet been elucidated. As the crystal structure of a transmembrane protein is very difficult to obtain and has not been achieved to date for full-length FeoB, we have decided to investigate the putative Fe(II)-binding sites of FeoB protein in the form of peptidic models. [3,4] Utilizing various physicochemical methods, such as potentiometric titration, mass spectrometry, NMR, EPR, and CD spectroscopy, and molecular dynamics, we have characterized the Fe(II) complexes formed with peptide fragments of the FeoB. We present the stability of the complexes, their stoichiometry, and the Fe(II)-binding residues, as an important insight into both the metal-binding properties of the FeoB protein and the Fe(II) coordination chemistry.

Figure 1. Scheme of bacterial Fe(II) transport system Feo.

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Tailoring Synthetic Siderophores for Precision Pathogen Targeting and Molecular Imaging Applications

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Under iron-deficient conditions most aerobic microorganisms secrete low molecular-weight chelating compounds – siderophores, which actively transport ferric ions into the cells via specific transporters in the microbial membranes [1, 2]. The difficulties in synthesis of structurally complicated natural siderophores has directed us towards biomimetic chemistry, aiming at mimicking or reproducing the function of the natural product rather than its detailed structure. This approach allowed us to diversify the arsenal of biologically active siderophore-type molecules, introduce additional desired chemical and/or physical properties, and provide means to identify general motifs governing an interplay between structure and function in biological activity [1-5].

Taking into account, that siderophores are absent in the host cells, they are tempting targets for microbial imaging, for example with ⁶⁸Ga or ⁸⁹Zr using positron emission tomography (PET) [5]. Of the evaluated siderophores, ⁶⁸Ga-ferrioxamine E and its close biomimetic analogues were shown as the most promising for possible applications in PET imaging of *S. aureus* and *A. fumigatus* species [4, 6]. Currently we are working on other bacterial (*P. aeruginosa*) and fungal species, to better understand the *in vivo* speciation and differences in the biological recognition and uptake of these artificial siderophores.

Interestingly, under specific conditions siderophores are also able to bind other metal ions and act as selective metallophores. In this context, we currently examine siderophores possessing aryloxazoline and arylthiazoline units [2].

Overall, mimics of siderophores may hold potential as inert and stable carriers for Fe(III), Ga(III) and Zr(IV) ions for diagnostic medical applications. They could also allow identifying critical microbial compartments in which siderophores accumulate and thus illuminate key targets for specific drugs against microbial diseases.

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PEG-grafted Metal-organic Frameworks for Imaging: The key parameters for robust synthesis of stable nano-formulations.

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Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) constitute outstanding candidates among nanocarriers in medical imaging, due to their unique properties, including ultra-high surface area, permanent porosity, multifunctionality and facility in chemical modification.^[1] Post-synthetic functionalisation of MOFs' surface with ligands, such as phosphate-functionalized methoxy polyethylene glycol (mPEG-PO₃) groups, is a promising strategy for developing biocompatible nanomaterials.^[2] In the present work, UiO-66 was selected as an archetypal MOF to investigate the effect of PEG grafting on nanoparticle stability and the incorporation of PET/MRI inorganic clusters was studied. UiO-66 NPs with different morphologies were synthesised *via* the solvothermal method, by adjusting key parameters (e.g., modulator type, metal precursor). Each MOFs' structure, size and shape were confirmed by Powder X-ray Diffraction, IR and TEM. To evaluate their colloidal stability, hydrodynamic size of all materials was monitored over the time in biological buffers using Dynamic Light Scattering, UV-Vis and TEM. Finally, the incorporation of NaF was investigated as analogous salt of PET tracer Na¹⁹F by NMR and SEM. Our systems were found to be stable under biological conditions over the time and accumulate NaF into the porosity of the nanomaterials, making them outstanding candidates for future imaging applications.

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DACH-based hexadentate ligands for Pb²⁺ complexation: towards applications in nuclear medicine

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With the increasing number of cancer cases, improving treatment techniques is crucial. Among all, the use of radiometals has gained increased attention, particularly, targeted alpha therapy (TAT) has drawn a significant interest due to the intrinsic properties of the alpha particle itself, i.e. very high linear energy transfer (LET) and a short path length. These properties make alpha particles effective in the treatment of hypoxic tumours, radio-resistance cells, micro-metastatic diseases and rapidly growing cancers [1, 2]. However, emerging alpha-emitters, like actinium-225 (²²⁵Ac, $t_{1/2}$ = 10.0d), bismuth-212/213 (²¹²Bi, $t_{1/2}$ = 60.55 min; ²¹³Bi, $t_{1/2}$ = 45.61 min) lack suitable diagnostic isotopes. A rare unique opportunity of an alpha-emitter which can be paired with a chemically identical diagnostic isotope is represented by lead isotopes, lead-212 (²¹²Pb, $t_{1/2}$ = 10.6 h) and lead-203 (²⁰³Pb, $t_{1/2}$ = 51.9 h) [2], respectively. ²¹²Pb decays via β^- particle emission to the α -emitting daughter ²¹²Bi, making it valuable as an *in-situ* generator of ²¹²Bi. Being a borderline soft metal ion, Pb²⁺ preferentially binds to donor atoms such as nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen. To date, the [^{203/212}Pb]Pb²⁺ complexation has been performed with the octadentate macrocyclic 1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane-1,4,7,10-tetraacetic acid (DOTA) and its amide derivative TCMC (or DOTAM)[3]. Despite their use, challenges remain in preventing the dissociation of the metal, especially for DOTA, and in retaining the daughter radionuclide ²¹²Bi, which tends to accumulate in the kidneys, for both DOTA and TCMC [3, 4]. Recent studies have focused on developing new systems, especially acyclic, with different donor atoms [1, 2].

This work presents the development of ligands containing a “rigid” *trans*-diaminocyclohexane (DACH) scaffold, aimed at enhancing both thermodynamic and kinetic inertness through a pre-organized structure. H₂bpcd and NH₂bpcd [Fig. 1] are DACH-based hexadentate ligands that differ only by the type of pendant arm used, carboxylic and amidic, respectively. H₂bpcd has been reported in literature for Ga(III) complexation [5], but it has never been used for Pb²⁺ complexation [5].

Figure 1 Structure of ligands in this work. R = OH, H₂bpcd; R = NH₂, NH₂bpcd.

The ligands were successfully synthesized, characterized via ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-NMR and LC-MS(IT) spectroscopies. Pb²⁺ complexation was studied mainly via ¹H NMR spectroscopy, following spectral changes upon metal addition in different buffered media (pH 2, pH 4.4, pH 7.4 and pH 9). Rapid complexation

was observed over a broad pH range, even in acidic conditions. To assess the kinetic inertness of the Pb^{2+} complexes, acidic-mediated dissociation kinetic experiments were also performed,

Figure 2. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra of $\text{Pb}^{2+}\text{-NH}_2\text{bpcd}$ complex at different pH

(* water residual peak; # buffer residual peak)

coordination environment.

For potential clinical applications, further studies will be performed to assess the ability of these chelators to bind Bi^{3+} , daughter of ^{212}Pb decay, as well as to be radiolabelled with ^{203}Pb or ^{212}Pb .

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demonstrating that complexation occurred until reaching extremely low pH values: pH 1 and pH 0.5 for H_2bpcd and NH_2bpcd , respectively. Interestingly, the ^1H NMR spectra revealed multiple species for the complex $\text{Pb}^{2+}\text{-NH}_2\text{bpcd}$ [Fig. 2], whose distribution is independent from the pH, while H_2bpcd showed one predominant species in solution at acidic pH.

Ongoing studies aim to elucidate Pb^{2+} -complexes structures both in solution and in solid state, giving further insight into the

Influence of Ligand Topology on the Physicochemical Parameters of Rare-Earth Metal Complexes of OCTAPA Derivatives

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Trivalent rare-earth complexes are promising candidates for both diagnostic (MRI) and therapeutic (β^- therapy) applications due to their unique properties. Among them, paramagnetic Gd(III)-based complexes contribute to MRI imaging efficiency as contrast agents (CAs). In addition, the optimal half-lives and emitted β^- energy levels of the ^{90}Y and ^{177}Lu nuclides make them attractive for radiopharmaceutical applications. Complexation of these metal ions with open-chain ligands presents a challenge in achieving sufficiently high kinetic inertness, in contrast to certain macrocyclic ligands or bispidine derivatives.[1,2] The case of the H_4OCTAPA ligand family clearly demonstrates the impact of the ligand backbone on kinetic inertness. For instance, replacing the ethylenediamine spacer in H_4OCTAPA with a cyclohexane-1,2-diamine unit in $\text{H}_4\text{CHXOCTAPA}$ resulted in a six orders of magnitude increase in the half-life of Gd(III) complex dissociation (at pH 7.4, $[\text{Cu}^{2+}] = 1 \mu\text{M}$), from 0.15 h to 1.49×10^5 h, compared to the corresponding H_4OCTAPA complex.[3] In recent studies, it was also observed that the topology of the ligand may significantly influence the most relevant physicochemical parameters of the complexes.[4,5]

In this work, we synthesized a new octadentate chelator, $\text{H}_4\text{CHXOITAPA}$, which can be regarded as a derivative of H_4OCTAPA , to explore the effect of ligand topology on the physicochemical properties of rare-earth(III) metal complexes. The protonation constants of CHXOITAPA^{4-} were determined by pH-potentiometric titration, and the overall basicities of the CHX analogues were found to be similar. Due to the formation of rare-earth(III) complexes even at low pH (~ 2), relaxometric titration was used to determine their stability. First, the

stability of the $[\text{Gd}(\text{CHXOITAPA})]^-$ complex was determined ($\log K_{\text{GdL}} = 21.47(4)$) by following the decreasing relaxation rate during the formation process. Then, titration of the Gd(III) complex with the corresponding diamagnetic Y(III) and Lu(III) ions enabled determination of their stability constants. The obtained values ($\log K_{\text{YL}} = 21.24(5)$ and $\log K_{\text{LuL}} = 21.96(1)$) were higher than those reported for other OCTAPA derivatives.

Detailed dissociation kinetic studies were conducted by monitoring transmetallation reactions with Cu(II) ions using UV-Vis spectrophotometry. For all complexes studied, the acid-assisted dissociation rates were higher than those of the symmetric CHX-chelator, indicating slightly less inert complexes. However, it is important to note that the Cu(II)-catalyzed dissociation pathway was found to be almost negligible.

The radiolabeling of the ligands (Scheme 1) with ^{90}Y and ^{177}Lu showed remarkable results: at room temperature, quantitative labeling was achieved in just 10 minutes. Furthermore, the human serum stability (at 37 °C) of $^{177}\text{Lu}[\text{Lu}]\text{CHXOITAPA}^{4-}$ appears to be the most promising among the OCTAPA derivatives.

In conclusion, our results highlight that the central spacer and topology of the chelator play a crucial role in designing ligands for rare-earth complexation.

Scheme 2: Structures of ligands discussed in the present work

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Ferrocene-containing ionic liquids as catalysts of ring-opening polymerization

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Our interest in ferrocene-containing ionic liquids (Fc-ILs) follows an extensive investigation of transition-metal-containing ionic liquids (TM-ILs), which began with the discovery of a strong magnetic field response of the paramagnetic iron-containing ionic pair [Bmim][FeCl₄], which is liquid at room temperature [1]. TM-ILs are usually classified as task-specific, as their role goes beyond that of a solvent. They have found application in various fields, such as organic syntheses [2], electrochemical sensing [3], and analytical microextractions [4]. Recently, we have shown that TM-ILs based on iron [5], cobalt [5] and vanadium [6] are efficient catalysts for epoxy-anhydride ring opening copolymerization.

Scheme 1: ferrocene-containing ionic liquids bearing imidazolium and triazolium rings.

In the present study, four series of azolium-based Fc-ILs were synthesized on half-gram to ten-gram scales (Scheme 1). They were characterized by analytical methods, including multinuclear NMR spectroscopy, infrared spectroscopy, mass spectrometry, and differential scanning calorimetry. The electrochemical properties of the representative structures were investigated by cyclic voltammetry. In particular cases, molecular structures were determined by X-ray diffraction analysis on a single crystal. The catalytic effect was investigated on the system epoxide - cyclic anhydride for all synthesized Fc-ILs, revealing a significant role of the azolium ring on the ring-opening copolymerization.

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From Solution Equilibria to Photocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution: Exploiting Thermodynamics Concepts in Contemporary Catalysis

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It has already been argued that energy availability has been a major factor in human societies [1]. For a long time, the more energy was accessible, the better. Until, quite recently, we recognized the environmental issues brought about by current energy policies and the need to resolutely move away from non-renewable resources and greenhouse-gases-generating fossil fuels. On a non-trivial ground, somewhat relevant to the spirit of the ISMEC meetings, the issue of granting sustainable energy for everyone is exquisitely thermodynamic in nature.

There is, though, another relevant aspect in the necessary green transition. One needs to propose not only smart ways to harness energy from renewable sources (in this work, the Sun), but also methods that make use of benign and non-energy intensive manufacture methods.

Herein we report on the preparation of a robust composite photocatalyst for the water reduction reaction, *i.e.* a material that ultimately allows the storage of solar energy as the dihydrogen (H₂) molecule; this is convenient as either in fuel cells, or in traditional direct combustion, the release of stored energy would produce only H₂O as the reaction product.

Notably, the preparation of such composite photocatalyst has been achieved at room temperature in water, *i.e.* under very green conditions, exploiting a supramolecular step by step assembly which makes use of a series of spontaneous processes.

First, graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) are decorated with suitable ligands via spontaneous Langmuir-type monolayer formation in aqueous solution mediated by strong π - π stacking interactions.

The ligand itself was chosen due to its structure and acid-base properties (studied in solution with potentiometry and UV-Vis spectroscopy) and intended as an upgrade of previous work [2]. The non-aromatic portion of the ligand, *i.e.* the [9]aneN₃ macrocycle, is also

notoriously fit to bind metal cations; those explored here in terms of binding constants are Cu(II) (in lieu of the kinetic inert Pd(II), that could not be studied) and Cd(II).

The GNPs-Ligand hybrids can then spontaneously bind Pd(II) ions from aqueous solution, so that obtaining GNPS-Ligand-Pd(II) material requires no external energy input.

The almost stoichiometric amount of Pd(II) ions can then be displaced from their macrocyclic complex by addition of sulfide (S^{2-}) anions, *i.e.* exploiting a solubility product, again without energy-intensive methods. The controlled precipitation from the supported complexes allows for the formation of extremely small PdS nanoparticles (2 nm or below), due to the homogeneous scattering of the metal cations on the macrocycle-decorated surface.

In the last step Cd(II) ions are added, again affording Cd(II) macrocyclic complexes at the surface. Complexed cations are precipitated as CdS in a series of careful coordination/precipitation steps to afford the final material, which has a GNPs-Ligand: PdS: CdS composition of $\approx 4.5:95:0.5$ % (*i.e.* it has an extremely little loading of Pd).

The material was built in such a way that the surface adsorption of the ligand, pivotal for depositing the sulfides semiconductors, also transforms the GNPs material from a conductor to a semiconductor. PdS, finely dispersed into the CdS matrix, is both a better visible light absorber than CdS and works as a sink for the photogenerated holes in CdS. As a result, the photoinduced charge separation in CdS is stabilized enough to be very effective in water reduction, achieving a stable $4.05 \text{ mmol} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ H_2 generation under solar simulated conditions. Such significant H_2 production showed no signs of time dependency over a period of 28 h. A brief schematization is offered in Figure 1.

Figure 1. A scheme of the working principle of the catalyst.

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Heme vs. Cobalamin, Iron vs. Cobalt – and Beyond: Rationalization of Differing Reactivity in Redox and Coordination

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Although the coordination chemistry of metal-corrin complexes with redox agents has been traditionally restricted to reductants [1], we have recently found that cobalamin (vitamin B₁₂) forms complexes with some of the most common oxidizing agents in bioinorganic chemistry – hydrogen peroxide, organic peroxides / peroxyacids, hypochlorite, and chlorite. Using spectroscopic (UV-vis, NMR, resonance Raman, fluorescence) and computational ((TD)-DFT, QM/MM, dynamics) we rationalize why this chemistry happens much more slowly in cobalamin compared to heme / hemoproteins. Catalytic intermediates in (myelo)peroxidases, globins and chlorite dismutases are taken as reference – with unexpected findings for the latter. Also explored is the issue as to why the opposite is true for lower “super-reduced” oxidation states, which are more readily observed in cobalamin and the related coenzyme F₄₃₀ than in heme. In other words, “why cobalt in vitamin B₁₂ (and not iron, manganese, nickel, or copper, for instance)?”. Biomedical implications of the findings are considered.

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Tailoring antioxidant activities: Metal-type dependent, highly efficient SOD or catalase mimetics

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Oxidative stress is a pathogenic condition associated with a range of detrimental health issues including Huntington's, Parkinson's and Alzheimer's diseases.[1] The failure of the therapeutic administration of SOD enzymes to prevent oxidative stress has fostered the development of metal complexes capable of mimicking its activity.[2,3] Here, two new pyridine azacyclophane ligands capable of coordinating Cu^{2+} and Fe^{2+} to give rise to mimetics with high activities towards disproportionation of the superoxide anion or hydrogen peroxide, depending on the metal ion, will be presented. Whereas the Cu^{2+} complexes have some of the highest SOD activities reported to date, they are completely inactive towards H_2O_2 disproportionation. In contrast, the Fe^{2+} complexes catalyse disproportionation of H_2O_2 without showing any catalytic SOD activity. Therefore, the type of antioxidant activity of these macrocycles is dictated by the nature of the metal ion, which represents a new approach to the development of potentially useful mimetics.

Scheme 1. Representation of the ligands structure and abstract of the analysed activities.

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From enantiomeric exchange to antimicrobial activity: the enzymatic secrets of salivary peptides

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The interaction between metal ions and antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) is a fundamental aspect of designing innovative bioinspired antimicrobial agents, offering new possibilities for overcoming antibiotic resistance [1]. Human salivary AMPs, particularly those derived from the MUC7 protein, are essential to the innate immune system and act as a primary defense against pathogens. Their antimicrobial activity is significantly enhanced when they form complexes with metal ions [2]. Due to their broad-spectrum action and low possibility of inducing resistance, AMPs are promising candidates for new therapeutic approaches. However, their clinical use is often restricted by limited enzymatic stability, which necessitates developing peptidomimetics to improve their stability and antimicrobial properties [3].

In this study, we investigate the enzymatic stability, thermodynamics, coordination behavior, structural properties, and antimicrobial activity of Cu(II) and Zn(II) complexes with salivary proline-rich peptides and their D-amino acid-substituted analogs (**Figure**).

Figure: Simplified structure of mucin (left) with highlighted relevant fragments. Analyzed peptidomimetics of the FPN peptide (right), with enzymatically vulnerable regions marked in color. Lowercase letters in the sequence indicate D-amino acids.

A comprehensive analytical approach, integrating potentiometric titration, spectroscopic techniques (UV-Vis, CD, EPR), mass spectrometry, and HPLC, was employed to investigate

the coordination behavior and stability of metal-peptide and peptidomimetic complexes. Biological assays further assessed their antimicrobial potential.

Our findings reveal that metal coordination preferences vary depending on the applied modifications. Enantiomeric substitution of amino acids significantly enhances the thermodynamic stability of Cu(II) and Zn(II) complexes, while the enzymatic stability of partially modified peptides remains unchanged. Notably, the fully D-amino acid analog exhibits exceptional resistance to proteolysis and, when complexed with metal ions, demonstrates the most favorable minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values, underscoring its potential for antimicrobial applications.

This study underscores the significance of enantiomeric modifications in regulating metal-peptide interactions and enhancing the stability of antimicrobial peptides. These modifications represent a promising strategy for the development of next-generation antimicrobial agents with improved therapeutic efficacy.

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Formation, decomplexation and isomerisation mechanisms of lanthanide(III) complexes of 18-py₂N₄Ac₄ (H₄pyta): a large macrocycle for large metal ions.

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Complexes of macrocyclic ligands are utilized in medicine as MRI contrast agents or radiopharmaceuticals. To be used *in vivo*, they may not release the metal ion – they must be kinetically inert. Current nuclear medicine considers also radioisotopes of heavy (*i.e.* large) metal elements as they are *e.g.* therapeutic α -emitters.[1] But there are not chelators specially designed for the metal ions. Some years ago, macropa (**Figure 1**) was suggested as a ligand for the ions [2, 3] and it initiated studies of this ligand family. However, the ligands contain ether oxygen atoms which are not a good donor atoms and the structures are generally too flexible and, thus, more rigid ligands with nitrogen donor atoms (as better donors) should exhibit improved properties.

A large hexaaza macrocycle with four acetate pendant arms, 18-py₂N₄Ac₄ (H₄pyta; **Figure 1**), could be a suitable ligand. The ligand has ten donor atoms and is rigidified by two pyridine rings. It was prepared a long time ago [4, 5] but only sparingly studied till now.[6] Only recently, radiochemical studies have confirmed convenient properties of radiolabeled complexes with several metal radioisotopes.[7,8]

Figure 1

To study effect of metal ion size on properties of H₄pyta complexes, Ln(III) ions were chosen. The Ln(III) complexes were found to be present in several isomeric forms: *40* and *22* (CN 10, all donor atoms are bound) and *21* (CN 9, one pendant is not coordinated) – see **Figure 2**. The complexes are formed under relatively mild conditions, comparable with those for formation of Ln(III)-H₄dota complexes. The *40* isomer is a kinetic species (formed through an *out-of-cage* intermediate) which re-arranges to thermodynamic final complexes, *22* or *21*.

Depending on Ln(III) ion and reaction conditions during the syntheses, different mutual ratios of the final complexes were observed. The 40 species are formed in a fast base-catalyzed reaction and their slow isomerization to the thermodynamic species is acid-catalyzed process. This unique three-step complex formation was confirmed by kinetic data, multinuclear NMR studies and DFT calculations. The thermodynamic 22/21 isomers are extremely kinetically inert.[9] Kinetic inertness of the 22 isomers is 10^2 – 10^4 -times higher than that of [Ln(dota)]⁻ complexes (decomplexation in 5 M HClO₄ at 90 °C takes up several hours). In the highly symmetric 22 isomers, the metal ion is perfectly wrapped by the ligand and it prevents access of protons to the ring amine groups. The mechanism is supported by data from thermodynamic, kinetic, multi-nuclear NMR, UV-Vis and solid-state studies.

The results suggest that H₄pyta can be considered as a leading scaffold for the future development of ligands intended for large metal ions from the bottom of the Periodic Table.

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Structural diversity in zinc(II) complexes with substituted adamantane-1-carbonyl-N-hydrazinecarbothioamides

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The World Health Organization has recognized antimicrobial resistance as one of the top 10 global public health threats facing humanity. In this context, it becomes clear that there is a need for new and effective pharmaceuticals against resistant pathogens. The field of Inorganic Medicinal Chemistry can help with this, taking advantage of the inherent versatility of coordination and organometallic chemistry, for instance, through the coordination of bioactive organic molecules with strategically positioned donor atoms to different metal centers [1,2]. Our group has a long history of developing metal complexes in the search for novel anticancer compounds, having obtained several promising ternary copper(II) complexes with dipeptides and phenanthroline derivatives [3-5]. Recently, we have been focused on applying this experience to the design of novel potential antimicrobials using adamantancarbothioamides with zinc(II) and diorganotin(IV) as metal centers.

In this work we present the synthesis and characterization of two novel adamantane-1-carbonyl-N-hydrazinecarbothioamides substituted with an ethyl (L1) and benzyl (L2) group and their corresponding zinc(II) compounds. The zinc(II) atom sits on a pentacoordinate environment with square pyramidal geometry, with two antiparallel ligands in the equatorial plane coordinated through an amide N and a carbonyl O. This arrangement is supported by an intramolecular N-H \cdots O bond. The apical position is completed with a S atom of a ligand connected to a contiguous zinc(II) as can be observed in Figure 1. Interestingly, this small difference in the substituent generated two very distinct arrangements in the solid state for the complexes, ZnL. The ethylic ligand gave rise to the formation of 1D chains whereas the benzylic one stabilized a dinuclear form of the complex as evidenced by their crystal structures. The supramolecular landscape changes because of a 30° rotation of the ligands coordinated to one zinc atom with respect to the ones coordinated to the contiguous one in the structure of ZnL1, favoring the formation of the 1D chains. Meanwhile, the presence of a benzyl group allows for C-H \cdots π interactions with the adamantane group of a neighboring complex stabilizing a parallel packing of the ligands and formation of a discrete dinuclear moiety in ZnL2. Hirshfeld surfaces and average contact distribution within it also supports this observation.

Figure 1. Combined Ortep at 50% probability and wireframe representation for ZnL1 (a) and ZnL2 (b). Color code: O (red), N (lilac), C (grey), S (yellow), Zn (light grey). H atoms are omitted for clarity.

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Self-Assembly Interactions of pyridyl functionalised **btp** ligands with *d*- and *f*- metals

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The world of self-assembled metallosupramolecular architectures has continued to grow at an exceeding pace in the last number of years. Especially, from the labs of Crowley, Goldup, and Leigh, who have all explored the terdentate ligand [2,6-bis(1, 2,3-triazole-4-yl)pyridine] (**btp**) with the creation of eloquent self-assembled ligands. The Gunnlaugsson group have also been involved with the synthesis of **btp** structures with various *d* and *f* elements, by exploring their properties both in solution and solid state. With the work of Hegarty exploring the Ln-based **btp** polymers [1], Byrne probing the chiroptical properties of lanthanide-directed self-assembly **btps** [2] and McCarney work on Ln- supermolecular metallo gels based on the **btp** motif [3]. Crowley designed a pyridine functionalized **btp**, which showcased the ligand's beautiful crystal orientation with *d*-metals [4]. Building on this framework, our work is based on this **btp** system and the creation of coordination complexes formed with *f*-elements of Tb(III), Eu(III) and Lu(III). We have also synthesised a 3-pyridine **btp** structure to investigate the coordination with the nitrogen atoms and the resulting change in binding and strength with the switch of the position of nitrogen within the pyridine ring. In order to investigate this, Ln(III) titrations were carried out to observe the change in absorbance, fluorescence and phosphorescence upon the addition of Ln(III). The lifetimes of the complexes were recorded along with the q-values being determined. These studies were completed, performing morphological studies in different solvent systems. Crystallography of the structure has also been examined for both ligands and complexes.

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Bioaccumulation and speciation of Cobalt in *Mytilus galloprovincialis*: insights into metal-biomolecule interactions in a marine sentinel organism

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Understanding metal complexation in biological systems is key to assessing environmental and toxicological impacts of trace elements.[1,2] In this study, we investigate the speciation of cobalt, including the radionuclide ^{60}Co , bioaccumulated in the marine mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis* following *in vivo* exposure in a pseudo-natural system.[3] Cobalt is a relevant activation product released by the nuclear industry, and its interaction with biomolecules influences both its bioavailability and toxicity. Mussels from two contrasting sites (polluted Toulon Naval Base vs. unpolluted Villefranche-sur-Mer, France) were exposed to radiolabeled cobalt, and organ-specific accumulation was quantified using gamma spectrometry and ICP-MS. The highest accumulation occurred in the byssus and hepatopancreas, suggesting distinct biological roles and detoxification strategies.

To elucidate cobalt speciation, we combined bulk X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XANES/EXAFS), micro-XRF imaging, and nanoscale secondary ion mass spectrometry (nano-SIMS). Our data revealed Co(II) coordination with thiol-rich ligands in the hepatopancreas, consistent with metallothionein complexation, and a possible interaction with *Mytilus* foot protein (mfp-1) in the byssus. These findings provide insight into the coordination environment of cobalt in biological matrices and its selective binding pathways. This work highlights how speciation studies at organ and subcellular levels can contribute to a mechanistic understanding of metal transport, storage, and detoxification in marine organisms, with broader relevance to environmental and radiochemical risk assessment.

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Recovery of neodymium and praseodymium from waste magnet via solid phase extraction with natural zeolite

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Rare earths elements (REEs) are critical raw materials (CRMs) with high current demand in manufacturing sectors such as automotive, telecommunications, electronics, aerospace, defense and renewable energy. This wide variety of applications is related to their magnetic, catalytic and optical properties [1]. In particular, neodymium (Nd) and praseodymium (Pr) are key ingredients in the most powerful magnet material, namely neodymium-iron-boron (NdFeB). This magnet is used to manufacture permanent magnet synchronous generators, which are used in the major wind turbine configurations, traction motors and robotic technology [2]. Due to their high cost, low recycling rates and high dependence on other foreign markets, the recovery of these CRMs is of great interest and importance [3]. In order to recovery REEs from waste magnets, hydrometallurgical process shows advantages such as efficient separation of metals, reduced polluting emission and low energy consumption [4]. Hydrometallurgical processes include methods such as leaching, chemical precipitation, liquid-liquid extraction and solid-phase extraction [5]. Zeolites have been widely used in the separation of metals [6] due to their good selectivity for the exchange of different cations, large contact surface, high ion exchange capacity and a suitable tetrahedral pore structure. In addition to their low cost, they are available in large volumes and show excellent stability to chemical and thermal processes, that allow their reactivation and use in several cycles [7,8]. In this work, the extraction of Nd^{3+} and Pr^{3+} is proposed using a natural zeolite of the clinoptilolite type. The separation was carried out in batch mode, reaching a maximum sorption capacity at pH 6, sorbent dose of $2 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ and 90 minutes of contact time. The pseudo-second-order Ho model [9] was found to be more suitable for interpreting the sorption kinetics, suggesting separation via chemisorption, in particular an ion exchange mechanism. The isotherms obtained at temperatures of 20, 50 and 70°C presented an L-shaped shape indicating a possible progressive saturation of the sorbent through a single separation mechanism. The sorption equilibrium is well fitted by the Langmuir isotherm, indicating adsorption on a homogeneous surface with the formation of a monolayer of the sorbent. Increasing the temperature did not introduce significant changes in the sorption capacity, reaching a maximum capacity of 8.8 and 14.8 $\text{mg} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ for Nd^{3+} and Pr^{3+} . For concentrations above 100 $\text{mg} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ the selectivity of the sorbent for Pr^{3+} is greater than Nd^{3+} .

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Environmental applications of biologically active transition metal complexes

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Transition metal complexes of salen derivatives, mainly those bearing Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Pd, and Pt (Fig. 1), have been and still are the major focus of our research group. These complexes are of particular interest for their tunable binding strength and selectivity toward double-helical and G-quadruplex DNA structures [1,2]. Such DNA-binding properties have often been related to their *in vitro* anticancer activity. Recently, we have found that copper(II) salphen-like complexes are efficient catalysts for oxidation reactions in presence of oxygen peroxide, promoting the epoxidation of styrene as well as the oxidation of guanines in G-quadruplex DNA [3].

Salen metal complexes are also catalyst for the oxidation of olefins to epoxides. In this regard, we are currently investigating their potential as catalysts for the “one-pot” oxidative carboxylation of olefins, in which olefine epoxidation is a first step to capture carbon dioxide and convert it to cyclic carbonates. In this presentation, our approach will be described, involving the use of density functional theory calculations, high performance computing, and machine learning, to select the best combination of metal ion, ligand shape and substituents for improving their catalytic activity toward carbon dioxide capture and conversion.

Figure 1: Structure of generic Salen-like metal complexes

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Complexation and Precipitation Equilibria in the Cadmium(II) – Nicotinic Acid System. A Potentiometric, Spectrophotometric and ^{113}Cd - NMR study

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Cadmium is a highly toxic element used in Ni-Cd batteries, pigments, and polymer stabilizers. It enters the environment through fertilizers, industrial processes, and fossil fuel combustion[1], contaminating water and soil and accumulating in the food chain with severe effects on living organisms. Modeling Cd^{2+} complexation with biological ligands is crucial for targeted chelation therapy. Nicotinic acid (pyridine-3-carboxylic acid, HL), a water-soluble B vitamin, offers carboxylate and pyridine nitrogen as coordination sites. Known for its lipid metabolism benefits, its interaction with Cd^{2+} in aqueous solution remains poorly explored. Existing speciation data are limited and often report questionable stability constants[2]. The study aims to provide a detailed investigation of the complex formation equilibria between Cd^{2+} and nicotinic acid in a 3 M $(\text{Na})\text{ClO}_4$ ionic medium at 25 °C, determining the stoichiometry and stability of the formed complexes, identifying the coordinating donor atom(s) of the ligand, and characterizing any solid phases that precipitate.

The complexation equilibria have been investigated using a combination of glass membrane electrode-based potentiometry, UV-Vis spectrophotometry, and ^{113}Cd -NMR spectroscopy.

Potentiometric experiments were conducted as titrations at (25.00 ± 0.03) °C in a 3 M $(\text{Na})\text{ClO}_4$ ionic medium to maintain constant activity coefficients. Due to the Cd^{2+} - nicotinic acid complexes being weak, soluble species represented a low percentage of total Cd(II). This implies that variations of the measured potential are primarily due to the deprotonation reactions of the ligand. Considering that ligand's protolysis constants would significantly impact the proposed complexation model, it became essential to determine the acid dissociation constants of nicotinic acid with the highest accuracy. Therefore, a study has been conducted at different ionic strengths (1 M, 2 M, and 3 M NaClO_4) to enable the extrapolation of the two protonation constants of the ligand to zero ionic strength, based on the Specific Interaction Theory. Protonation constants in 3 M NaClO_4 have been further validated by spectrophotometric titrations. The formation constants of Cd^{2+} -nicotinic acid complexes were determined by processing potentiometric titration data using both Hyperquad2008 and Letagrop programs. The best fit of the data was obtained assuming the $\text{Cd}(\text{HL})^{2+}$, CdL^+ , $\text{Cd}(\text{HL}_2)^+$, and CdL_2 complexes, with the formation constants reported in Table 1.

Table 1 Equilibrium constants for the Cd²⁺-nicotinic acid system at 25°C in 3 M (Na)ClO₄

Reaction	log(constant ± 3σ)
$\text{Cd}^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{L}^+ = \text{Cd}(\text{HL})^{2+} + \text{H}^+$	- 1.6 ± 0.1
$\text{Cd}^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{L}^+ = \text{CdL}^+ + 2\text{H}^+$	- 6.9 ± 0.1
$\text{Cd}^{2+} + 2\text{H}_2\text{L}^+ = \text{Cd}(\text{HL}_2)^+ + 3\text{H}^+$	- 7.4 ± 0.1
$\text{Cd}^{2+} + 2\text{H}_2\text{L}^+ = \text{CdL}_2(\text{aq}) + 4\text{H}^+$	- 13.5 ± 0.4
$\text{Cd}^{2+} + 2\text{H}_2\text{L}^+ = \text{CdL}_2(\text{s}) + 4\text{H}^+$	- 9.6 ± 0.1

Fig. 1 a) Distribution diagram for 10 mM Cd(II) and 10 mM Nicotinic acid. The fraction of Cd²⁺ is omitted for clarity. b) ¹¹³Cd-NMR spectra at 25 °C of 0.1 M Cd²⁺ with 0.1 and 0.2 M nicotinic acid, compared to 0.1 M Cd²⁺ reference.

In the $4.5 \leq \text{pH} \leq 5.6$ interval formation of a very low amount of the neutral species CdL₂ occurs, whose concentration is about 0.13 mM at pH 5.6 in the presence of CdL₂(s).

The solid phase that formed during titrations was isolated, washed, dried and characterized by EA, ICP-OES and ATR-FTIR. Elemental analysis and ICP-OES confirmed a stoichiometry of CdL₂·2H₂O. ATR-FTIR spectra of the solid showed the absence of the carbonyl stretching band characteristic of the non-coordinated carboxylic acid, indicating coordination through the carboxyl-oxygen atoms. To gain insight into the donor atoms involved in the coordination of the complexes in solution, ¹¹³Cd-NMR analysis was performed. The negative chemical shift observed, as with benzoic acid (oxygen donor), contrasts with the positive shift observed with pyridine (nitrogen donor), and strongly supports the coordination of Cd²⁺ by nicotinic acid through the carboxylate oxygen(s).

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How reliable is the evaluation of DNA binding constants? Insights and best practices based on an inter-laboratory fluorescence titration study

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In all experimental sciences, the precision and reliability of quantitative measurements are paramount. This is particularly true when examining the interactions between small molecules and biomolecules/polyelectrolytes, such as DNAs/RNAs, and yet it is overlooked in most publications of thermodynamic binding parameters. We will present findings that are part of the work of a network of researchers involved in this type of measurements, members of COST Action 18202 "Network for Equilibria and Chemical Thermodynamics Advanced Research". This study assessed the consistency of data derived from the interactions of calf-thymus DNA (CT-DNA) with the fluorescent intercalator ethidium bromide (EB) through spectrofluorimetric titrations.

We first discuss critical experimental aspects and propose a reference experimental protocol which can be used to calibrate procedures for the determination of nucleic acid binding equilibrium constants. We then fit the experimental point according to different procedures and analyse the results

focusing on the statistical dispersion of the data, aiming at enlightening the strong and weak points of different fitting procedures. The implications of this work are significant, demonstrating how the statistical dispersion of experimental data can influence the interpretation of biochemical coordination mechanisms. Our study reveals that, despite rigorous protocol standardization, the determination of binding parameters remains sensitive to the choice of data fitting method, with deviations in the logarithmic stability constant ($\log K$) values not falling below 5% relative standard deviation (RSD), or $\pm 0.5 \log K$ units for 95% confidence. This variability evidences the critical need for standardized best practices in data treatment as well as experimental procedures. Although our study focuses on the EB/CT-DNA system through fluorescence titrations, the broader implications for other methodologies across various biochemical systems highlight the importance of this first-of-its-kind inter-laboratory comparison in advancing our understanding of biochemical coordination processes.

Figure 1. Dispersion of $\log K$ values obtained in the first (SET I) and second (SET II) rounds of inter-comparison

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Ni(II) Cylinder Preferentially Binds DNA Three-way Junctions Blocking DNA synthesis and Triggers DNA Damage in Cancer Cells

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DNA three-way junctions (3WJs) are composed of three double-helical arms connected at a branch point. These alternative DNA structures form as intermediates during biological processes such as replication, repair, and recombination, but they are also involved in the development of various human degenerative disorders. Targeting and stabilization of DNA 3WJs by specific ligands holds significant potential for disease treatment and therapeutic applications. Moreover, high-affinity 3WJ probes could be useful in chemical biology and in the development of DNA nanostructures. Compared to traditional coordination metal complexes, structurally more elaborate 3D metallo-supramolecular architectures, such as metallo-supramolecular helicates, offer new opportunities for targeting alternative nucleic acid structures, which often contain binding pockets and cavities, as in the case of 3WJs [1], that can accommodate spatially demanding ligands.

We studied a metallo-supramolecular triple-stranded [Ni₂L₃]⁴⁺ cylinder (L = C₂₅H₂₀N₄) developed by Hannon [1] and our results show that [Ni₂L₃]⁴⁺ exhibits preferential binding affinity for DNA three-way junctions (3WJs), even in the presence of an excess of competing DNA structures, including G-quadruplexes, and that it was able to halt DNA synthesis catalyzed by DNA polymerase by stabilizing the 3WJ on the template strand [2]. We used an extended 1D nanoarchitecture model to confirm the high affinity and selectivity of the cylinder for DNA 3WJs and to explore its potential application in the construction of DNA nanomaterials. The combined use of [Ni₂L₃]⁴⁺ and DNA damage response inhibitors revealed that the cylinder promotes DNA damage, leading to the formation of double-strand breaks. This effect is likely associated with (i) the binding of the cylinder to 3WJs and (ii) the cytotoxic activity of the cylinder in cancer cells [2].

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Syntheses and metal ion binding strengths of novel ambidentate ligands to construct anticancer drug candidates with hypoxia activation

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Pt(II) anticancer drugs often cause serious side effects, due to lack of selectivity. One option to overcome this serious problem is the development of multitargeted metal complexes considering the significant differences between the physiological processes of cancer and healthy cells. Among others, hypoxia in cancer tissues results in a reductive environment allowing the selective reduction of inert, chaperon Co(III) complexes and release of biomolecules with e.g. anticancer, metalloenzyme inhibitory or iron(III) sequestering properties. Structural modification of these biomolecules bound in the Co(III) complexes enabling them to coordinate another platinum group metal ions with proven anticancer potential, may lead to further advantage and improved biological activity. For this purpose, ambidentate ligands may serve as useful building blocks.

In an ongoing project to develop heterobimetallic cobalt(III)-platinum group metal (Co/PGM) complexes with likely hypoxia activation and selective anticancer activity we have developed, synthesized and characterized various ligands incorporating isolated O and N donor sets, some of them being bioligand derivatives or derivatives of known drug molecules. With the combined use of pH-potentiometry, NMR and ESI-TOF-MS techniques we studied their interaction with [Co(4N)]³⁺ units (4N = tripodal 4N donor or 2x2N donor ligand), Pd(II) and organometallic Ru(II) or Rh(III) ions in solution and in the solid state. This contribution will summarize our recent results regarding the donor atom selectivity of the metal ions, the architecture, redox features and preliminary *in vitro* anticancer activity of the complexes [1-3].

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Novel ruthenium (II) polypyridyl complexes: synthesis, interaction with mitochondrial G-Quadruplexes and biological activity in HCT116 human colorectal cancer cells

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G-Quadruplexes (G4s), DNA secondary structures in guanine-rich sequences, are recognized for their roles in cellular biology and potential as anticancer targets [1]. Recent studies have also identified G4s in mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA), suggesting a potential regulatory role and opening new avenues for mitochondria-targeted cancer therapies [2]. Metal-based compounds, including Ru(II) complexes with dipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine (dppz) ligands, have high affinity for G4s [3,4]. Notably, *BOLD-100*, the first Ru-based drug in advanced clinical trials, shows promising anticancer activity [5].

To investigate the effects of G4-interacting compounds on mtDNA G4s, we synthesized a series of new Ru(II) complexes of the form [Ru(bipy)₂(L)], [Ru(phen)₂(L)] and [Ru(p-cymene)(L)Cl], where L is a dppz ligand functionalized with a triphenylphosphonium group for mitochondrial targeting (**Figure 1**). FRET melting assays revealed that the compounds strongly stabilize mtDNA G4s. Also, *in vitro* studies in HCT116 cells demonstrated a cytostatic effect, notably enhanced by co-treatment with the GLUT1 inhibitor *BAY-876*. Finally, Seahorse Mito Stress Assay confirmed significant impact on mitochondrial respiration in treated cells.

Figure 1: Structure of the newly synthesized compounds.

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Silver-binding to DNA containing 7-deazapurine nucleobases

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Metallizing well-organized DNA structures continues to pose a significant challenge in the scientific community.[1] In this work, we show that **modifying DNA with 7-deazapurine** enables the formation of **silver-mediated Watson-Crick base pairs** while preserving the native base-pairing geometry. In contrast to previous X-ray structures,[2] our solution-state analysis reveals that **Ag(I) incorporation does not disrupt canonical base pairing or DNA self-assembly**. Instead, the continuous Ag(I) coordination forms a helical pattern guided by the DNA backbone, rather than adopting a conventional linear metal chain arrangement. In this study, we present structural insights derived from **NMR, CD, UV-Vis,** and thermodynamic analyses using **ITC**

Figure 1: Right) Three-dimensional structure of a DNA duplex with continuous silver-modified base pairs. Left) Schematic representation of the non-canonical Metal-Mediated base pairs **X-Ag^I-T** and **C-Ag^I-Y** (**X**=7-deazaadenine, **Y**= 7-deazaauanine). Inset: Replacement of the N7 position in X and Y by a carbon atom (CH).

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From scratch to speciation: exploring the aqueous coordination chemistry of 2-(aminomethyl)-quinolin-8-ol

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Historically, 8-hydroxyquinoline (8-HQ) and its derivatives played a significant role in chemistry and biology, primarily due to their effective metal-chelating abilities [1]. Whether 8-HQs are used as metal-sensing probes or studied as therapeutic agents, their performance and potential applications are strongly influenced by their potency and selectivity in metal coordination. Various substitutions on the aromatic ring of 8-HQ have been proposed to enhance or modulate their chemical and biological activities. Substitutions on the aromatic ring have been introduced to tune their structure–activity relationships, improve metal binding affinity, or direct selectivity towards specific metal ions or target(s) in solution.

Speciation studies of metal ions in the presence of 8-HQs are essential for elucidating their coordination abilities and distribution in solution [2]. A detailed understanding of the stoichiometry and structures of the resulting complexes under varying conditions is critical for assessing the role of 8-HQs in both environmental and biological systems. Therefore, speciation is essential to rationalize and optimize the chemical and biological functions of 8-HQs.

In this context, 2-(aminomethyl)-quinolin-8-ol (AMQ, reported in Scheme 1) was synthesized and thoroughly studied. Its structure was confirmed by ESI-MS and ¹H-NMR spectroscopy.

Scheme 1 - 2-(aminomethyl)-quinolin-8-ol (AMQ) structure

Protonation behavior was examined in aqueous solution through H⁺-ISE potentiometry, UV-vis spectrophotometry and ¹H-NMR pH-dependent experiments at 0.2 mol·dm⁻³ KCl and 298.15 K, revealing the deprotonation order of the three protic sites and allowing the determination of

the protonation constants. These data were compared with the earlier observations for AMQ reported by Stevenson et al. (1967) [3] in H₂O/dioxane (50:50) mixture, showing good agreement while providing a more complete and accurate description of the protonation behavior in aqueous solution.

Fe³⁺ and Cu²⁺ chemical speciation in presence of AMQ was investigated in 0.2 mol·dm⁻³ KCl_(aq) and 298.15 K. H⁺-ISE potentiometry and UV-vis spectrophotometry were exploited.

AMQ exhibits weak interaction with Fe³⁺ in aqueous solution, with FeOH_{3(s)} occurring at pH > 5. Nonetheless, speciation was defined in the range 1.7 < pH < 5, and formation constants for Fe³⁺-AMQ species were determined. On the other hand, AMQ displays excellent chelating ability towards Cu²⁺, forming stable complexes across a wide pH range. It has been noticed that speciation strongly depends on the metal-to-ligand ratio in solution. At 1:1 ratio, low stoichiometry species such as [Cu(AMQ)]⁺, its hydrolytic derivative and a protonated complex were observed. At higher ligand excess (1:2, 1:3, 1:4), higher stoichiometry species form, and for pH > 9 precipitation of a complex species occurs. The stoichiometry of the solid species was defined, and its solubility product (K_{sp}) was determined via ICP-OES.

Species distributions were traced for the investigated systems and the speciation models of AMQ with Fe³⁺ and Cu²⁺ were critically compared with those of 8-hydroxyquinolin-2-carboxylic acid (8-HQA) [4], which differently from AMQ contains a carboxylic acid group at the 2-position. This comparison underscores the importance of the substituent in position 2 of 8-HQs in modulating their selectivity and potency as tridentate metal chelators.

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Host-guest complexes in aqueous solution: insights on the molecular recognition properties of carboxylato-prism[*n*]arene containers

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Naphthalene-based macrocycles have recently attracted considerable attention in supramolecular chemistry due to their unique structural and conformational features. In particular, a new class of deep-cavity macrocycles, termed prism[*n*]arenes (*n* = 5 and 6) [1], along with their water-soluble derivatives bearing carboxylato groups on both the upper and lower rim (PrS[*n*]carboxy), have been synthesized and thoroughly characterized [2].

Understanding the driving forces that govern the molecular recognition processes in aqueous solution remains one of the major challenges in supramolecular chemistry. The structural and conformational properties of water-soluble hosts as well as the nature, charge, size, and shape of the guest molecules play a critical role in determining the stability constants of the binding equilibria in solution [3].

Within this framework, we investigated the host–guest complexes formed by water-soluble carboxylato-prism[*n*]arenes (*n* = 5, 6) with a large set of aliphatic and aromatic molecules (quaternary ammonium ions, amines, ethers, ketones, etc.) in aqueous solution at 25 °C and pH 7.6 by isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) measurements.

Key insights on both the binding affinities and the energetics of the recognition processes have been obtained. The macrocyclic hosts form 1:1 complex species with all the investigated guests, with stability being strongly affected by the specific properties of the interacting molecules. The determination of the enthalpic and entropic contribution to the Gibbs free energy revealed interesting aspects on the driving forces of the complexation equilibria and their dependence on host and/or guest features [2,4].

More recently, the carboxylato-prism[6]arene has been proposed as a catalytic scaffold for the oxidation of aromatic amines into the corresponding nitro derivatives for potential use in scalable and sustainable catalysis. Thermodynamic characterization of the host–guest interactions provided key information on how number, position, and nature of substituents affect the complexation mechanism and the driving forces of the process.

Overall, this work offers a comprehensive thermodynamic perspective on understanding and predicting molecular recognition events in water involving prism[*n*]arenes, revealing essential insights for applications in sensing, separation, and catalysis.

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Metal Ions And Peptides – A Bioinorganic Symphony For Antimicrobial Action

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Unraveling how metal ions influence antimicrobial peptides (AMPs), our work offers new insights that may contribute to the field of beautiful, fundamental bioinorganic chemistry. We show that coordination of Zn(II) and Cu(II) ions to AMPs can significantly enhance their antimicrobial activity by modulating peptide structure, morphology, and local charge.[1]

Our project revealed, for the first time, that Zn(II) binding to amyloidogenic peptides such as pramlintide, amylin analogs, and shepherdin induces the formation of amyloid fibrils, which appear to underlie their potent antifungal effects. This “coordination-induced fibrillization” proceeds via a clear trajectory: distal metal binding → structural rearrangement → fibril formation → antifungal activity. This insight introduces a new perspective on the role of functional amyloids in antimicrobial action.[2]

In the case of piscidins or semenogelins, we show that their antimicrobial effect arises from the locally cationic character of their metal complexes, which promotes interactions with negatively charged microbial membranes.[3,4]

Together, these findings deepen our understanding of metal-peptide interactions and may offer a foundation for the rational design of metal-based antimicrobial strategies. By bridging molecular coordination chemistry with mechanisms of microbial resistance, we hope to take one tiny small step toward addressing a major medical challenge.

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PULIDORI AWARD 2025**Master Survival Strategy: Aspf2 zincophore and ZrfC transporter on the front line in the battle for the host's Zn(II)**

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Rapidly spreading antimicrobial resistance is a serious problem and a global threat to modern society. The invention of penicillin revolutionized medicine, but now, in many cases, treatment of bacterial and fungal infections turns out to be impossible. Thus, we have to introduce new, highly selective drugs. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to understand one of the biggest differences between human and pathogen cells - mechanism of Zn(II) uptake, which is a good starting point to design a highly specific antifungal drug.

Aspergillus fumigatus is a well-adapted saprophytic and opportunistic fungal pathogen, that produces many small airborne spores and proliferates in the lungs of immunocompromised patients. It causes, among others, invasive pulmonary aspergillosis, whose mortality rate may reach up to 90%. To survive in the host, *A. fumigatus* uses a highly specified Zn(II) transport mechanism based on peptide zincophore Aspf2 and zinc transporter ZrfC. This mechanism of Zn(II) uptake is one of the critical aspects of fungal virulence and survival and distinguishes fungal cells from mammalian ones.

After the invasion of the host cells, *Aspergillus fumigatus* secretes an extracellular zincophore Aspf2, which is released into surrounding host cells, where it binds Zn(II) and delivers it to the fungal pathogen through physical interaction with the ZrfC transporter (Figure 1). The most probable Zn(II) binding site on Aspf2 zincophore is its C-terminal region, PNCHTHEGGQLHCT.

Figure 1. Schematic model of *Aspergillus fumigatus* Zn(II) scavenging from host cells. After invasion of the host cell, Aspf2 is expressed and secreted. It binds Zn(II), either in the form of free Zn(II) or from Zn(II)-binding proteins of the host. Reassociation with the *Aspergillus fumigatus* cell surface and Zn(II) transportation into the cell occurs via a Aspf2-ZrfC interaction.

At physiological pH, pH 7.4, it binds Zn(II) via a $\{2N_{im}, 2S^-\}$ binding mode. The most probable binding site for ZrfC transporter is the MNCHFHAGVEHCIGAGESESGSSQ fragment, which, at physiological pH, binds Zn(II) via the same set of donor atoms as the fragment of the Aspf2 zincophore. Thus, both fragments coordinate Zn(II) via two histidine imidazoles and two cysteine thiolates with the $\{2N_{im}, 2S^-\}$ binding mode [1, 2]. Nevertheless, the ZrfC fragment coordinates Zn(II) with higher affinity than the Aspf2 fragment [2], and it allows efficient Zn(II) transport from the zincophore to the transporter (Scheme 1). The same fragments also have a high affinity towards another essential for fungi metal ion, Ni(II), that can compete with Zn(II) for its binding sites. However, even in a theoretical situation in which equimolar amounts of both metals would be available, the Aspf2 zincophore strongly prefers to bind Zn(II) over Ni(II). At physiological pH, more than 85% of the PNCHTHEGGQLHCT fragment is coordinated to the Zn(II). The situation is different in the case of the ZrfC fragment, where more than 58% of the sequence prefers to bind Ni(II). It makes the selectivity of this transporter much more complicated and interesting. All the more so because the ZrfC protein could be essential for obtaining Zn(II) from the host environment and holds promising expectations to find novel therapeutic strategies.

Scheme 1. Schematic model of zincophore-based transport mechanism in *Aspergillus fumigatus*

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ANDRÉS M. DEL RÍO AWARD 2025**Solar-thermal energy release in a water-soluble push-pull norbornadiene-derivative triggered by a Co(II)-porphyrin complex**

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Various technologies have been developed to harness solar energy as a renewable resource to address the increasing global energy demand. In this context, Molecular Solar-Thermal (MOST) energy storage systems have emerged as promising candidates, particularly for overcoming the intermittency inherent in conventional solar technologies. MOST systems rely on molecular photoswitches capable of capturing, converting, storing, and releasing solar energy in a closed, emission-free, and on-demand fashion. Notably, the norbornadiene/quadracyclane (NBD/QC) couple is one of the most extensively studied. However, its practical application has primarily been confined to organic solvents. Although water-soluble NBD derivatives have been reported, they typically exhibit poor spectral overlap with solar radiation.

Building upon these efforts, we synthesized a new NBD derivative incorporating a push-pull electronic system to enhance solar absorption and a hydroxamic acid moiety to ensure full-range aqueous solubility (Figure 1). The protonation constant has been potentiometrically determined: the properties of the system were evaluated for the neutral hydroxamic acid (at pH 6), and the hydroxamate species (at pH 11). The deprotonation of the push-pull system improved both spectral properties and solubility, but at the expense of the quantum yield and stability compared to the neutral NBD state.

In both cases, we exploit the photochemical NBD/QC equilibrium using 310 nm light, yielding almost quantitative isomerization. This equilibrium was observed to be under kinetic

control with a half-life of 61 days (QC⁻) and 18 days (HQC) at 298 K, enabling energy storage over extended periods. Interestingly, upon exposure to a Co(II) complex of 5,10,15,20-*tetrakis*(*p*-carboxyphenyl)porphyrin (Co-TPPC, Figure 1), the stored energy was rapidly and quantitatively released, restoring the parent NBD and releasing the stored energy on demand. Due to the high catalytical turnover, accurate kinetic analysis via NMR was not feasible, as the QC converted too rapidly under both acidic and alkaline conditions. The efficient catalytical back-conversion was then used to assess the heat-release profile of the system.

While energy storage density of MOST systems is usually evaluated in the solid-state via differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), here we employed isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) to quantify the stored energy directly in aqueous solution, thus resembling the conditions relevant to device application (typically in solution). We used 2 %mol CoTPPC to achieve quantitative back-isomerization of the water-soluble QCs to the parent NBD at pH 6 and 11. This catalyst, previously reported by Maruyama in the 1980s [1] and more recently by our group [2], enabled robust and reproducible thermal characterization.

We determined energy densities of 297(2) kJ·kg⁻¹ at pH 11 and 279(2) kJ·kg⁻¹ at pH 6, confirming the efficiency of the back-conversion in both cases. These values are consistent with the energy density determined via differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) in the solid state (304 kJ·kg⁻¹). The close agreement between solution and solid-state data underscores the reliability of ITC for the evaluation of aqueous MOST systems under practical conditions.

Overall, our findings demonstrated the feasibility of employing push-pull functionalized NBD derivatives in aqueous solution under carefully controlled pH conditions. Moreover, they open avenues for enhancing MOST systems through the use of green solvent mixtures, aligning with the principle of sustainable molecular design.

Figure 1. Summarized results of the study of HNBD as a MOST system in aqueous solution.

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Electrochemical synthesis of cluster helicates with biomedical potential

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Helicity is a fundamental and widespread motif in nature. Inspired by this, chemist have done significant effort to the design and synthesis of artificial helical architectures that mimic these features. Among these, metallo-helicates have attracted significant attention due to their unique functional properties and broad potential across different disciplines, particularly in the biomedical field [1,2]. In 2005, our research group introduced a novel class of metallo-helicates, known as cluster helicates (Figure 1), synthesized through an electrochemical synthesis strategy. Since then, a wide array innovative examples of cluster helicates has been reported, thereby demonstrating their structural diversity and expanding scientific relevance of this topic [3].

To further advance the development of cluster helicates, we rationally designed a family of thiosemicarbazone ligands with different terminal substituents. These ligands feature two flexible bidentate [NS] coordination sites that are connected by a rigid aromatic spacer, favouring the development of helical architectures. Using an electrochemical methodology, we successfully prepared Cu⁺ and Ag⁺ cluster helicates. Notably, several of the synthesized cluster helicates exhibited promising biological activity, highlighting their potential for therapeutic and diagnostic applications.

Figures 1: *The design of artificial helical motifs inspired by nature.*

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Peptide Inhibitors of Metalloproteinases: Structural Insights into Complexes with Zinc and the Catalytic Domain

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Metalloproteinases are a diverse group of enzymes involved in the hydrolysis of peptide bonds, playing crucial roles in both physiological and pathological processes. They are found across a wide range of organisms, including bacteria, where alongside other proteins [1], they contribute to virulence, and humans, in whom their dysregulation is implicated in cancer progression and tissue remodeling. Despite their biological diversity, metalloproteinases share a conserved catalytic mechanism. The metal ion is typically coordinated by three histidine residues in a conserved motif, stabilizing the catalytic site and facilitating proton transfer during catalysis [2].

Given their involvement in various diseases, metalloproteinases are attractive targets for therapeutic intervention. Peptide-based inhibitors offer a promising strategy due to their structural flexibility and potential for high specificity [3]. Our research focuses on the rational design of such peptide inhibitors, aiming to selectively target metalloproteinases through coordination with the catalytic metal center [4, 5]. In this context, we investigate the formation and stability of ternary complexes involving the enzyme domain, zinc ion, and peptide inhibitor [6]. Using a combination of potentiometric titrations, spectroscopies, and computational methods, we explore the binding modes and structural determinants of inhibitor affinity, with the goal of advancing bioinorganic strategies for metalloproteinase inhibition.

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Comparing the Bioinorganic Chemistry of MUC7 Fragment and Its Peptidomimetics: Distinct or Similar?

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Salivary mucin, MUC7, involved in the body's innate immune defense, is naturally cleaved into peptide fragments in saliva, some of which exhibit potent antimicrobial activity.[1] However, their therapeutic potential is limited by rapid enzymatic degradation. To overcome this challenge, a native MUC7-derived peptide was chemically modified using D-amino acids and a *retro-inverso* strategy to enhance its stability without compromising its function.[2]

L1: K S H F E L P H Y P G L

L2: k s h f e l p h y p g l

L3: l g p y h p l e f h s k

Figure 1: Amino acid sequence of native MUC7 fragment (L1) and its peptidomimetic modifications (L2 and L3).

Given the known role of metal ions in modulating antimicrobial peptides [3], we explored the coordination chemistry and biological activity of both native and modified MUC7 fragments with Cu(II) and Zn(II) ions. A comprehensive suite of techniques - including potentiometric titrations, UV-Vis, circular dichroism (CD), EPR, NMR spectroscopy, mass spectrometry, and DFT calculations - was employed to characterize metal binding, peptide structure, and stability.

Our findings reveal that *retro-inverso* and enantiomeric modifications preserve the peptides' secondary structure and antimicrobial efficacy, while significantly enhancing their thermodynamic stability, especially upon metal coordination. [4,5]

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Peptide-Based Inhibitors Targeting MMP for Cancer Suppression: Thermodynamic and Structural Insights into Zn(II)-MMP-Inhibitor Ternary Complexes.

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Cancer metastasis, the final stage of tumor progression, accounts for nearly 90% of cancer patients' morbidity and mortality. Conventional cancer treatment faces a significant challenge in delivering therapeutic drugs directly to cancer cells while minimizing damage to healthy tissues. One promising approach is to inhibit matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), zinc-dependent enzymes¹, overexpressed in cancer cells². Among them, membrane-type 1 matrix metalloproteinase (MMP14) plays a pivotal role in tumor invasion and angiogenesis by facilitating extracellular matrix breakdown and activating other proteolytic enzymes. Given its critical function, MMP14 represents an attractive therapeutic target for selective inhibition³.

This study aims to explore the coordination properties of MMP14's active site and its peptide-based inhibitors, with a particular focus on their interactions with Zn(II) (Tab. 1). The first stage involves comprehensive characterization of binary Zn(II)-MMP14/inhibitor complexes by determining stoichiometry, donor atom preferences and thermodynamic stability across wide pH levels. These analyses provide fundamental insights into the metal-binding characteristics of the inhibitors and establish a baseline for understanding their behavior in more complex systems. The second stage extends this investigation to ternary Zn(II)-MMP14-inhibitor complexes, determining their formation, stability, and coordination modes through potentiometry, Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations, and NMR spectroscopy.

Table 1. Amino acid sequences of the examined metalloproteinase domain and inhibitors³.

MMP14	Ac-VHELGHALGLEHS-NH ₂
Inh1	H-SDMAHSLPGHSH-OH
Inh2	H-EREAHQLHSHHK-OH
Inh3	H-TQARHQPHYTIA-OH
Inh4	H-HHDHHA AVGGGGGGGGA-OH

Potentiometric data revealed a correlation between binary complex stability and ternary complex formation. Inhibitor Inh1, which formed the most stable Zn(II)-inhibitor binary complex at pH 8.0, also exhibited the highest stability in ternary systems with Zn(II)-MMP14. These results were also confirmed by DFT analyses. Computational modeling identified two

primary Zn(II) binding modes by the inhibitor in the ternary complexes: one through histidine nitrogen and the other through oxygen from Asp/Glu side chains. NMR spectroscopy confirmed that Asp1 in Inh1 directly participates in Zn(II) coordination within the ternary complex, reinforcing its role in stabilizing MMP14 interactions.

These findings enhance the understanding of Zn(II)-targeted MMP14 inhibition and identify key structural features for designing selective inhibitors. The correlation between binary and ternary complex stability provides a basis for predicting inhibitor efficacy. By integrating thermodynamic, spectroscopic, and computational approaches, this study supports the rational design of MMP14 inhibitors with potential applications in cancer therapy. Peptide-based strategies targeting MMP may offer a promising approach to suppress tumor progression while minimizing off-target effects.

Figure 1. The structures of the Zn(II)-MMP14-Inh1 complex and graphical representation of Inh1 docking to the MMP14 catalytic domain.

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Exploiting Knowledge from Solution Chemistry to Search for Research Funding

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Solution Chemistry is not only a topic, but a strategic backbone that impregnates many aspects of our research activity, including knowledge creation, methodology development, applications to problem solutions and scientific education.

However, there is one aspect of our daily activity that has taken a central role in the last decades: *sustainability* and scalability of research itself. This not only refers to promoting a critical mass of scientists, but also to securing the update of infrastructures and facilities required to remain competitive and at the forefront of innovation.

Such *sustainability* demands have reshaped the classical scientist role. Today, a good scientist is not only the one who generates brilliant ideas, but also the one who transform those ideas into funded research, being capable of convincing funding entities to develop high-impact projects, and sustaining long-term knowledge generation. This is far from trivial as public and private programs have evolved into problem solving frameworks that demand alignment with societal, industrial, and environmental challenges, often requiring a clear path to technology transfer and real-world implementation.

This evolving scenario has shifted the basic research unit from a classical researcher to interdisciplinary, agile research groups, where members take on specialized roles, including scientific leadership, stakeholder engagement, and project management. In this context, we will present some selected case studies that have evolved from solution chemistry knowledge to successfully funded research projects in competitive research programs both of EU and Spain.

- RECOPHARMA (H2020): Deeping into sorption/desorption processes to recover highly valuable toxic cytostatic compounds at trace levels from polluted wastewaters.
- NEOSETAC (H2020): How Selenium chemical species can help on breast cancer treatment.
- RAWMINA (H2020): Translating coordination chemistry insights into novel hydrometallurgical approaches to process mining waste.
- CuWINE (Spanish Ministry -RETOS Program): Tuning lixiviation processes to recycling winery waste for selective recovery of metal content (mostly Copper and Zinc) and clean waste as fertilizer.

These examples illustrate how the knowledge from solution chemistry can unlock funding opportunities by connecting fundamental science to urgent societal needs, from circular economy to human toxicology.

We aim to stimulate a dialogue around how the solution chemistry community can more deliberately align its research language, methodologies, and impact pathways with funding strategies, ensuring that the field continues to grow and lead in both scientific and economic dimensions.

PyES 2.0 – a solution to optimize stability constants from potentiometric data with unique features

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PyES 2.0 (PyES - Python Equilibrium Species) is an open-source, practical, modern and multi-platform Python application for concentrations calculation and for optimization of stability constants processing potentiometric experimental data. It is the extension of a previous version [1] able to simulate titration curves and plot species distribution diagrams that can handle both precipitation and solution equilibria. The ES4 [2] and BSTAC [3] software were used as a reference from which the design of PyES was moved. The reason that made the two software an ideal starting point is due to the fact that they have functionalities not present in other free software: i) they take into account the variation of the ionic strength in the system, a critical aspect to correctly estimate the concentration of the species; ii) they implement error propagation to return results with an uncertainty interval on the final concentrations. In PyES 2.0 the ability to optimize stability constants from potentiometric data was developed. It has been envisioned with a modular structure at its core, thanks to the development of a library, LibEq, that contains the core functionalities of the software. PyES can handle many titrations at the same time, each one with its specific components concentration, calibration data and pH range. Moreover, it can work with both weighed and unweighted least squares method. PyES 2.0 can calculate the concentrations of the different species using the stability constants corrected for the change of the ionic strength of the system as the previous version, and it can manage titration conducted at different ionic strength or in which the ionic strength is not strictly constants. To take into account the dependence of activity coefficients on system conditions a model based on an Extended Debye-Hückel equation [1] is used. Various tests were performed to verify the reliability of PyES with very satisfying results. PyES is user friendly and compatible with existing operative systems. The input data can be easily entered as .cvs files, the results are immediately displayed as a text or a plot, and they can be easily exported as .png, .xlsx or .csv files. Thanks to the modularity of the written routines, future new functionalities

could be easily implemented expanding the scope of the software itself. The availability of the source code makes it continuously improvable by the scientific community.

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Potentiometric investigation of solution equilibria in the Sn²⁺-H₂O-F⁻ system using Glass membrane, Fluoride Ion-Selective and Sn(Hg) amalgam electrodes

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Solution equilibria of tin in the +2-oxidation state are very difficult to study, owing to the relatively easy oxidation of the element to Sn(IV). In aqueous solutions, Sn²⁺ is a quite acidic ion, as it results from the study of its hydrolysis, widely investigated through several techniques, including potentiometry. [1-3] Although most of the authors agree on a speciation model in which, depending on the total concentration of tin(II), polynuclear complexes play an important role, the stability constants reported seem not consistent.

The available data have so far been interpreted assuming the existence of mononuclear species SnOH⁺, Sn(OH)₂ and Sn(OH)₃⁻ at low concentrations of tin(II) (< 0.5 μM), while, at higher metal concentrations polynuclear species predominate. [4] Of considerable importance are the species that Sn(II) forms with halides, and in particular, binary complexes with fluoride widely used in the cosmetic industry and specifically, in toothpaste formulations as a source of fluoride. [5] Ternary species formed by Sn²⁺ with hydroxide and some halides, Br⁻ and Cl⁻ have also been reported, while, up to now, studies concerning the formation of mixed ternary species Sn²⁺, OH⁻, F⁻ are absent. [6-8] Therefore, the study investigates the hydrolysis of Sn(II), the formation of binary Sn-F complexes, and the speciation of mixed Sn²⁺-OH⁻-F⁻ species in 3 M NaClO₄.

Table 1. Summary of the formation constants values of all the species determined in this work

Reaction	log(constant ± 3σ)
Sn ²⁺ + HF = SnF ⁺ + H ⁺	1.47 ± 0.02
Sn ²⁺ + 2HF = SnF ₂ + 2H ⁺	2.13 ± 0.04
Sn ²⁺ + 3HF = SnF ₃ ⁻ + 3H ⁺	2.47 ± 0.05
Sn ²⁺ + H ₂ O = Sn(OH) ⁺ + H ⁺	-3.61 ± 0.02
2Sn ²⁺ + 3H ₂ O = Sn ₂ (OH) ₃ ⁺ + 3H ⁺	-6.075 ± 0.004
2Sn ²⁺ + 2H ₂ O + 2F ⁻ = Sn ₂ (OH) ₂ F ₂ + 2H ⁺	6.28 ± 0.03
2Sn ²⁺ + H ₂ O + 3F ⁻ = Sn ₂ (OH)F ₃ + H ⁺	12.45 ± 0.03
Sn ²⁺ + 2OH ⁻ = Sn(OH) ₂ (s)	24.98 ± 0.03

Potentiometric titrations with NaF were carried out while simultaneously monitoring the concentrations of free H⁺, Sn²⁺, and F⁻ ions using a glass membrane electrode (GE), a tin amalgam electrode, and a fluoride ion-selective electrode (ISEF), respectively.

The constants determined in this work are summarized in Table 1, while the distribution of the different species as a function of pH is reported in Figure 1.

Additional insights into complex formation were obtained through ^{19}F -NMR spectroscopy.

Figure 1. Speciation $\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{F}^-$ system at 25°C
 Sn(II) : 10 mM, total
species are reported, up to the pH at which the formation of solid Sn(OH)_2 occurs.

diagram in the Sn^{2+} -
in 3 M NaClO_4 . Total
 F(-I) 5 mM. Soluble

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Dirhenium(III) clusters of biological interests

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The chemistry of compounds containing metal-metal multiple bonds was considered as one of the most fascinating chapters in modern coordination chemistry [1]. The electronic structure of metal–metal-bonded compounds continues to enlighten our understanding of bonding; metal–metal-bonded compounds may be used in important applications: as structural subunits of metal–organic frameworks, molecular-scale conductors, photosensitizers, catalysts [2]. Several comprehensive reviews compile the biological effect of different rhenium complexes according to their oxidation state [3,4]. In our previous research, summarized in [5], we provided an overlook of design, biological activity *in vitro* and *in vivo* of the quadruple-bonding cluster dirhenium(III) complexes, preferentially with di- and tetra-alkyl-carboxylate ligands.

Dinuclear rhenium(III) compounds with metal-metal bond belong to the class of d^4-d^4 dimers that have electronic configuration of $\sigma^2\pi^4\delta^2$ in the ground state according to quantum chemical calculations, the order of the metal-metal bond is 4 and in the case of an electron capture is 3.5.

Depending on some conditions of the synthetic procedure it was possible to obtain dirhenium(III) derivatives: octahalogenides (**I**); dihalogenotetra- μ -carboxylates (**II**); trihalogenotri- μ -carboxylates (**III**); *cis*-tetrahalogenodi- μ -carboxylates and *cis*-di- μ -aminocarboxylates (**IV**); *trans*-tetrahalogenodi- μ -carboxylates (**V**); and Re_2^{6+} phosphates (**VI**). On the **Fig. 1** the synthetic linkage and interconversion of the types **I** – **V** of dirhenium(III) compounds is presented.

Fig. 1 Interconversion of dirhenium(III) carboxylates of the types **I** – **V**

Among known metal-based anticancer drugs and drug candidates dirhenium(III) compounds differ profoundly due to their non-toxicity, strong antiradical and antioxidant properties, shown *in vitro* and revealed *in vivo*.

Dirhenium(III) compounds have their own anticancer activity that is mainly conditioned by dirhenium cluster fragment but depends on the nature of the ligands; the synergistic effect in application of cisplatin and dirhenium(III) cluster compounds showed eliminated tumor growth and cancer cells with high efficiency; combination of two metal based compounds switched some additional signal transduction pathways crucial for cancer cells survival or death.

Dirhenium(III) clusters as antioxidants (δ , π – antioxidants in spite usual π – antioxidants) behaved as antihemolytics, hepato- and nephro- protectors. The idea of regulation of redox potential in cancer cells is one of the central in cancer treatment. Overall, the above results strongly indicate that application of nontoxic dirhenium(III) compounds with quadruple bond is an emerging concept in the development of new anticancer therapeutics.

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Poster Communications

Silver(I), Zinc(II) and Gallium(III) tiophene-2-carboxylates: HSA binding and thermodynamics study

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The thermodynamics of metal complexes is a crucial parameter in fields such as bioinorganic chemistry, catalysis, environmental science and materials science [1]. In this study, a series of three tiophene-2-carboxylate (*Tio2c*) complexes using Ag(I), Zn(II) and Ga(III) as central atoms, $[Ag(Tio2c)]_2$ (AgTio2c), $\{[Zn_2(Tio2c)_4]_2\}_n$ (ZnTio2c) and $[Ga(Tio2c)_3] \cdot H_2O$ (GaTio2c), were synthesized and studied for their binding and thermodynamics parameters with human serum albumin (HSA). HSA is the most abundant protein in plasma and plays a crucial role in the transportation of ions, lipids and drugs to biological targets [2]. An examination of the interaction between albumins and the novel complexes with small organic ligands could provide significant information about the biological activity of the compounds. The interactions of AgTio2c, ZnTio2c, GaTio2c and HTio2c with HSA were investigated using tryptophan (Trp) fluorescence emission quenching experiments. After the addition of AgTio2c, ZnTio2c, GaTio2c and HTio2c, the fluorescence intensity of HSA in the presence of the samples at room temperature was found to have decreased in the relation $HTio2c < GaTio2c < ZnTio2c < AgTio2c$. The K_b values were found to be in the order of $10^4 M^{-1}$, and this would indicate that the affinity of the interaction between the AgTio2c, ZnTio2c, GaTio2c and HTio2c compounds and HSA falls within the optimal range for the transportation and distribution of compounds within the organism. The thermodynamics of the binding between AgTio2c, ZnTio2c, GaTio2c and HTio2c and HSA were examined using monitoring fluorescence quenching at different temperatures. In order to provide further information on the binding energies involved in the formation of the complexes, the thermodynamic parameters (ΔH , $T\Delta S$, and ΔG) were calculated using van't Hoff equations. The negative ΔG values indicate that the binding of AgTio2c, ZnTio2c, GaTio2c and HTio2c with HSA is a spontaneous process. In addition, the positive values of ΔH and ΔS indicate that the binding interactions between AgTio2c, ZnTio2c, GaTio2c and HTio2c and HSA are primarily entropy-driven endothermic reactions in which hydrophobic forces play a major role. These results suggest that the AgTio2c complex would be the most suitable candidate for future biological applications. The knowledge gained will also serve as a basis for the creation of subjects for the new bachelor's degree program in biochemistry.

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Design and redox properties characterization of metal/tetrabrached peptide adducts as possible superoxide dismutase mimics

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The alteration in the human physiological redox balance can lead to the increase of reactive oxygen species (ROS), that results in oxidative stress condition, which can cause molecular damage and tissue injury. The protection from ROS naturally occurs by processes mediated by superoxide dismutases (SODs) and catalases (CATs). To reduce oxidative stress damage exogenous SOD and CAT have been used as therapeutic agents [1], although with limited success [2]. Their use is limited by some restrictions, such as low thermal and chemical stability, low adaptation to extreme environments, and expensive preparation and purification processes [3]. To overcome these limitations, investigations have been directed to the design of low molecular-weight antioxidant catalyst. Enzyme mimics (EMs) usually replicate the binding and catalytic activities of natural enzymes, employing: i) metal complexes with comparable catalytic properties, ii) oligopeptides that reproduce the active site structure of natural enzymes [4]. In this work both strategies were integrated to produce a EMs based on a synthetic tetrabrached structure composed by a scaffold (PWT2 – based on cyclam (1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradecane)) bound to four oligopeptides (Scheme 1) able to bind metal cations [5,6]. The synthesis of the tetrabrached PWT2-peptides has been achieved by binding four identical peptides on the PWT2 scaffold. The final tetrabrached systems is obtained in solution by reacting the maleimide functionalized scaffold PWT2 with the chosen peptides in a classic thiol-Michael reaction at room temperature and in the presence of a weak base, ensuring environmental and economical sustainable synthesis conditions.

P1 – AAHAWGC(S-Methyl)-NH₂

P2 – HAWGC(S-Methyl)-NH₂

P3 – AAHAWGELLKLLLEELKGC(S-Methyl)-NH₂

P4 – HAWGELLKLLLEELKGC(S-Methyl)-NH₂

Scheme 1 - Peptides synthesized and used to compose the tetrabrached systems.

The redox behaviour of single peptides and/or tetrabrached systems, and their complexes with Cu, Mn, Ni and V(IV)/V(V), have been characterized by means of cyclic voltammetry with the

aim to evaluate what chemical system can be considered good candidates to become EMs. In order to simulate the redox behaviour of SOD, in fact, the chemical species redox signals must be between the values -0.37 V and 0.71 V vs Ag/AgCl, with an optimal value at 0.16 V vs Ag/AgCl [7]. The CV measurements conditions were optimized. The main efforts were focused in increasing the sensitivity of the technique and reducing the needed sample volumes. Solid and screen printed electrodes were tested: Glassy Carbon Electrode, (GCE), Gold Electrode, (AuE), Gold Screen Printed Electrode (AuSPE), Carbon Screen Printed Electrode (CSPE), and Multi Wall Carbon Nano Tubes – Carbon Screen Printed Electrode (MWCNT-CSPE). Voltammetric signals were collected on aqueous solutions with: (i) peptide (1.0 mmol L⁻¹), (ii) metal cation 1.0 mmol L⁻¹ and peptide 1.0 mmol L⁻¹; (iii) metal cation and tetrabranched systems 1.0 mmol L⁻¹. Tetrabranched systems were tested at different metal-to-ligand ratios. The solutions were prepared in NaCl 0.2 mol L⁻¹ at pH 7.3. MOPS (3-(N-morpholino)propanesulfonic acid) was used as pH buffer. Since with the screen-printed electrodes it was possible to work with low amount of solution, they resulted to be particularly suitable to achieve the analytical goal. On the basis of the voltammetric response obtained with CSPE a priority level was assigned to each metal-peptides or tetrabranched system. The voltammetric parameters taken into account to assign the priority are the reversibility of the observed electrochemical process and the potential value related to this process. On the basis of the experimental results the most promising systems are those involving P1 and P3 peptides with copper and manganese, and the tetrabranched system composed with P3 peptide with copper.

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Fluorescence selectivity through structural modifications: new HNBO- and HBO-based chemosensors for metal cations in solution

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The design of receptors capable of selectively recognize and bind specific guests in solution is a timeless and challenging goal. To this purpose, we have recently synthesized a family of polyazaligands based on the HNBO fluorophore (2-(2-hydroxy-3-naphthyl)-4-methylbenzoxazole). The fluorescence mechanism is ESIPT-based and is influenced by the presence of a guest metal ion and nature of the solvent. The most promising molecule of the series (**L**, Figure 1) resulted selective for Mg²⁺ in DMSO solution [1], the other chemosensors changed their selectivity depending on the employed solvent, moving from Mg²⁺ in DMSO to transition metal ions in ACN [2].

Trying to optimize the sensing properties of such molecules, strategic structural modifications were brought (Figure 1). On one hand, the polyamine chain was modified to increase the number of donor atoms, by inserting additional amine and OH functions. On the other hand, the fluorophore moiety was modified, moving from HNBO to HBO (2-(benzo[*d*]oxazol-2-yl)-6-methylphenol), to increase the acidity of the OH group and the number of coordination bonds with the metal guest.

The proposed strategies allowed for the chemosensors to work in a less toxic solvent (EtOH) and to include in the study metal ions of the rare earth family, analytes that commonly require a greater number of interaction sites, some of which are considered critical raw materials (CRMs). Therefore, the newly introduced properties make these chemosensors possibly useful for the extraction of CRMs from solutions simulating e-wastes.

Figure 1: HNBO and HBO fluorescent chemosensors.

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Quantitative analysis of exosome-antibody interactions for optimizing molecular recognition in liquid biopsy

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Cancer remains a major societal, public health, and economic challenge in the 21st century, with millions of new cases and related deaths reported globally each year [1]. Early detection, disease monitoring, and treatment assessment are key to lowering cancer mortality. Though tissue biopsy remains the diagnostic gold standard, it is invasive and often limited in scope. In contrast, liquid biopsy offers a non-invasive alternative as it allows detecting tumor-related components such as circulating tumor cells, extracellular vesicles (EVs) and nucleic acids in blood or other fluids. This approach showed great potential for tracking tumor progression and identifying early signs of treatment resistance and recurrence [2].

Among tumor-related markers, exosomes, a subtype of EVs, are promising candidates since are stable in biofluids and their content reflects genetic or signaling changes in tumor cells [3]. However, accurately quantifying exosomes remains challenging since conventional techniques struggle to distinguish them from other EVs, protein aggregates, and lipoproteins [4].

As an alternative, biosensors capable of selectively capturing exosomes via antigen–receptor interactions have been developed, thus enabling more specific and efficient detection. To this aim, it is essential to identify optimal ligand–target pairs to enhance the molecular recognition process which depends on the strength and nature of the interactions, with a direct impact on the biosensor performance [5].

Within this framework, we addressed the quantitative analysis of the interactions occurring between surface biomarkers in breast cancer-derived EVs and selected target antibodies both in solution at the solid-liquid interface. The study focused on the recognition of tetraspanin CD63 and proteoglycan Glypican-1 (GPC1), both present on EV membranes and implicated in breast cancer diagnostics (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Schematic representation of an exosome with surface biomarkers.

Quartz crystal microbalance (QCM-D) measurements allowed real-time monitoring of frequency and dissipation changes during vesicle adhesion to gold sensors suitably functionalized with selected antibodies, providing detailed insights on the adsorption kinetics, bound mass and viscoelastic properties at the interface [6]. Complementary ITC experiments enabled a complete thermodynamic profile of the interactions in solution, offering a deeper understanding of the binding mechanisms involved.

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Antitumor platinum(II) complex 56MESS binds to DNA G-quadruplexes, downregulates expression of *c-MYC* and *k-RAS* oncogenes, and triggers DNA damage in cancer cells

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Previous research indicated that the cytotoxic activity of the antitumor platinum(II) complex [Pt(1*S*,2*S*-diaminocyclohexane)(5,6-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline)]²⁺ (56MESS) was not primarily attributed to DNA binding, despite the complex being confirmed to localize also in the nucleus [1]. In this study, we have demonstrated that the antiproliferative activity of 56MESS indeed involves DNA binding. Furthermore, in addition to binding duplex DNA, the complex also interacts with non-canonical secondary DNA structures, such as G-quadruplexes (G4s) and i-Motifs (iMs). This interaction leads to the suppression of G-regulated oncogene expression and disrupts key enzymatic processes associated with DNA, potentially contributing to DNA damage and the biological activity of 56MESS. These findings build upon previously published results, revealing that the anticancer activity of 56MESS is significantly more multifaceted than previously understood, involving multiple distinct mechanisms [2].

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The Effect of Novel Benzothiazole-1,2,3-thiazole Based Arene Osmium(II) Complex on Rhabdomyosarcoma Cells

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A series of pseudo-octahedral arene Os(II) complexes (Os1-Os5) (Scheme 1.) with the general formula $[(\eta^6-p\text{-cym})\text{Os}(\text{BTAT})\text{Cl}]^+$, where BTAT represents N^N' ligands based on the 1-aryl-4-benzothiazolyl-1,2,3-triazole scaffold, was designed and synthesized. Crystal structure was confirmed by X-ray diffraction using single crystals of Os3 and Os5.

Scheme 1. Molecular structure of pseudo-octahedral arene Os(II) complexes

The investigation revealed that the Os(II) complexes exhibit moderate antiproliferative effect across a panel of six cancer cell lines. Among these complexes, Os5 was identified as the most potent with activity comparable to or better than conventional cisplatin. Furthermore, Os5 in Rhabdomyosarcoma (RD) cancer cells, the most responsive cell line, exhibited the highest cellular accumulation where more testing confirmed that binding to human serum albumin did not play a significant role. Mechanism of action in RD cells includes mitochondrial dysfunction with loss of potential and morphology, apoptosis via a caspase-dependent pathway and cell cycle arrest at the G1 phase. In addition, Os5 demonstrated the capacity to induce production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which may be a contributing factor to the activity of Os5.

Antiproliferative effect of the complexes was also tested on 3D spheroid models of RD cells. It is particularly noteworthy that all complexes exhibited higher activity in stem cells than in non-stem cells spheroids, with Os5 being about two orders of magnitude more effective than cyclophosphamide, a drug used as chemotherapy agent in rhabdomyosarcoma. This marks the first report of an osmium-based compounds targeting CSC-enriched RD cells a emphasizes the potential of metal-based complexes as a chemotherapy agent targeting cancer stem cells [1].

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Fe(III)-loaded imprinted polymers: towards new catalytic materials for dye pollutant degradation

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The rapid growth of the textile industry has intensified ecosystem contamination, primarily from dye-laden effluents [1]. In the search for new effluent treatments, heterogeneous iron-catalyzed advanced oxidation processes emerge as a promising technology [2]. The aim of this work was to immobilize Fe(III) complexes in molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs), to produce efficient Fenton-like heterogeneous catalysts for the green oxidative degradation of dye pollutants in the presence of H₂O₂ [3]. Our study includes three dye pollutants from distinct families (Figure 1): methyl orange (MO, an azo dye), methylene blue (MB, a thiazine dye), and malachite green (MG, a triphenylmethane dye).

Figure 1. General strategy. The degradation percentages for the three dyes tested are included in color.

We first carried out a screening of a wide range of Fe(III) complexes with commercial and low-cost ligands, and their efficiency towards the discoloration of the dyes by H₂O₂ were assessed spectroscopically. We monitored the dyes' oxidative decomposition by following the

UV-vis absorption band of the dye over time in a solution containing the iron(III) complex and H₂O₂. The best candidates displayed very high dye degradation (> 70%) in 1.5 hours (see values of degradation percentages in Figure 1). Fe-BIDA excels in this regard, achieving over 96% degradation efficiency in just 20 minutes. To elucidate the chemical nature of the catalytic species in solution, we studied the chemical speciation using H⁺ potentiometry, combined with fitting spectroscopic data to kinetic models and assessing OH[•] radical formation via a TBARS assay. The results reveal two parallel or consecutive stages: one involving a hydroperoxide complex species and another associated with a pseudo-Fenton Fe(III)/Fe(II) cycle. Additionally, total organic carbon levels in the systems remain relatively stable, suggesting that dye degradation leads to organic products with lower molecular weights. We are currently analyzing their chemical nature using HPLC-MS.

The best complexes were then employed to imprint catalytic cavities into water compatible MIPs, using methacrylamide as a functional monomer and MBAA as crosslinker (Figure 1). The polymers were characterized using infrared spectroscopy, iron content analysis, and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Additionally, we computationally modelled their molecular structure, revealing the interactions that drive the imprinting process (Figure 1). The MIPs are robust, easy to isolate and can decompose the dyes with high efficiency (Figure 2). The best polymers (Fe-BMPA@MIP and Fe-DPA@MIP) achieve over 90% dye discoloration within 3 hours. Fe-DPA@MIP is able to degrade > 82% of the dyes in 1.5 hours.

Figure 2. Dye degradation percentages exhibited by the best polymers after 3 hours in the presence of H₂O₂.

We are now assessing the cytotoxicity of the decomposition products on VERO cells. The IC₅₀ values determined for the Fe-BMPA@MIP system show that, for MB and MG, the products are less cytotoxic than the dye. Besides, the non-imprinted polymers (having no complex inside) and the complexes in solution show low cytotoxicity. These MIPs constitute promising materials, in the search for efficient and low-cost wastewater treatment systems.

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Dispelling the myth of metal ions contamination in waste: making horse hoof trimming upcycling safe and sustainable

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Upcycling represents one of the major challenges nowadays, being a pivotal step in sustainable development, both for industry and academia. In recent years, the scientific community has shown a growing interest in upcycling strategies for various non-edible animal tissues, mainly due to their abundance and high keratin content. Mammalian sources such as wool, hair, nails, hooves, horns, and claws predominantly produce α -keratin, while bird feathers, quills, beaks, and fish or reptile scales yield β -keratin. [1] These materials, primarily by-products of slaughtering and butchering operations, are increasingly abundant, with keratin production from livestock alone reaching 11.82 million tons in 2020, mainly from chicken feathers and wool, containing approximately 95% and 90% keratin, respectively. [2,3]

In this context, horse hoof waste generated from regular shoeing and trimming offers a sustainable, traceable, and cruelty-free keratin source with distinct advantages. [4-6] This contrasts with cattle hooves, often prioritized in research solely to prevent pathologies and slightly more frequently investigated for upcycling strategies, leading to heterogeneous and lower-quality waste after slaughter. [7] Obviously, horse hoof trimmings represent a niche resource if compared to slaughtering-related waste: tentative estimates suggest a global yearly production of 106,000 tons, where 53 million sport horses undergo regular trimming. Despite the smaller scale, this waste stream's unique properties and potential applications should justify its targeted valorization. One of the main concerns limiting horse hoof upcycling is represented by the myth of heavy metal ions contamination as a result of shoeing practices: in fact, most of the papers dealing with these materials claim to have selected only barefoot horses to avoid the presence of metal ions in the extracted compounds. [6]

The aim of our preliminary investigation on these uncommon and generally overlooked materials is to provide a comprehensive knowledge of metal ions contamination in horse hoof waste, with a specific focus on its correlations with external factors such as horse characteristics, geographic origin, management and shoeing habits. Individual metals (Mn, Cu, Zn, Al, Fe, Cd, Pb, Cr, Ni) are quantified using Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES) after microwave digestion (800W) with nitric acid and hydrogen peroxide and Principal Components Analysis is applied to identify similarities or correlations in the overall metal content in different samples.

Additionally, different multi-step cleaning procedures are then designed by Plackett-Burman Design and tested in order to develop a sustainable but effective protocol to reduce metal ion contamination in horse hoof waste and make them a safe candidate for upcycling strategies. These apparent naïve experiments play a crucial role in improving the background knowledge on these materials and to promote their utilization as source of valuable compounds, dispelling the myth of hazardous heavy metal ions contamination, as demonstrated so long from our very preliminary results.

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Selective recovery of heavy metals from wine sludge using oxidizing agents: towards sustainable waste management in viticulture

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Vine mildew is one of the main fungal diseases affecting viticulture, compromising all the green organs of the plant and causing significant economic losses. In this context, the European Union, as the world's leading wine producer, faces a growing challenge in the sustainable management of vineyards. Traditionally, the control of fungal infections has been based on the intensive application of phytosanitary compounds based on copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn), which has generated a progressive accumulation of these metals in agricultural soils, vegetation and wine residues, representing a serious environmental and agro-industrial problem [1].

On the other hand, one of the most relevant current challenges in sustainable agriculture is the utilization of byproducts generated during winemaking, especially winery sludge. These residues are rich in organic matter and nutrients, making them potentially valuable for use as organic amendments in agricultural soils [2]. However, their heavy metal content, particularly copper, makes direct application in the field difficult.

To mitigate this impact and close the resource cycle, the selective extraction of these metals is proposed to recover copper as a fungicide, transforming it back into a useful resource for other processes or applications, rather than allowing it to pollute the environment (it is recovered, purified, and can be reintroduced into the industry). Sewage sludge, the residue from wastewater treatment, contains nutrients and other useful compounds of either potential use such as vineyard fertilizer, an energy source, or raw material for other uses that would otherwise be wasted.

In previous work carried out by our group, efficient extraction of Cu (90%) and Zn (95%) from wine sludge was achieved using sulfuric acid (0.5 mol/L) under mild conditions (room temperature, 1 h of stirring). Based on this finding, a sequential extraction strategy was designed to allow the separation of both metals in a stepwise manner.

Sequential extractions showed that the highest proportion of Cu was found in the oxidizable fraction, while Zn was found in the reducible fraction according to the BCR method [3]. Taking into account these findings, to produce an appropriate methodology for the selective lixiviation of these metal ions, we have studied the use of alternative, less polluting lixiviation agents able to accomplish this objective. To this purpose, various agents were tested, including

a H₂O₂/HNO₃ mixture (BCR), oxalic acid, and citric acid, the latter two being organic acids known for their effectiveness in recovering Cu from electronic parts and mining waste [4].

All tests were carried out under the same conditions as the H₂SO₄ extractions to ensure a direct comparison. The results showed that oxalic acid and citric acid were the most promising agents, allowing for a differentiated extraction of Cu and Zn. Oxalic acid showed greater affinity for Cu (0.117 mg/g) than for Zn (0.06 mg/g), while citric acid favored the extraction of Zn (0.086 mg/g) over Cu (0.034 mg/g), opening the door to the design of selective extraction strategies for each metal.

Currently, independent design of experiments (DoE) for both acids have been developed to optimize operating conditions (solid-liquid ratio, temperature, oxidizing agent concentration) to maximize the selective recovery of Cu and Zn. This approach promotes more efficient and environmentally friendly management of wine waste, aligning with the principles of the circular economy in the wine sector.

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From solution equilibria to 360° shelf-life: acid-base chemistry on act in freshness-sensing naked eye arrays

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The development of sensitive materials for food freshness/spoilage monitoring represents a hot topic in the last years due to the increasing demand for fresh and safe food products provoked both by population growth, lifestyle change, and globalization. [1] The wide variety of by-products released during degradation, their peculiar chemical properties and the range of atmosphere used for food packaging offer countless possibilities for shelf-life monitoring. Among all, the fine tuning of pH-sensitive devices does represent one of the most followed approaches since it assures several advantages: low cost of the receptors, naked eye visible color transitions, simple scale up and implementation in packaging, no need of dedicated instruments or readers and versatility towards various target food and packaging atmosphere. [2]

Such a widespread diffusion of this sensing approach, together with the large number of papers proposing similar devices, might suggest that pH-sensing devices for food spoilage monitoring can be developed without rational design behind but just randomly trying and testing. Indeed, deeply thinking about this application, anyone can immediately realize that it involves several temperature and pH-dependent processes are involved: i) food degradation, ii) by-products evaporation, iii) dye protonation or deprotonation. [3] For this reason, the development of similar devices should be driven by the application of solution equilibria principles and merging rational design with application on real samples.

An example of this strategy is clearly represented by sulfonephthalein-based colorimetric sensors developed by our research group in the last five years: depending on the type of target food and the corresponding degradation process and volatilome composition, we exploited pH-sensitive dyes with various pKa values to follow the ongoing spoilage. [4-12] We first focused our attention on meat and fish products [4-7,10-12] and we later moved to milk [8,9] and, more recently, to Ready-to-eat vegetables and fresh dairy products, as summarized in Figure 1. Differently from other devices proposed in literature, we are able to ensure such a wide versatility thanks to the application of solution equilibria chemistry principles in the selection of the promising sensitive dyes depending on degradation mechanisms and spoilage by-products type and behavior.

Figure 1: Overview of sulfonephthalein-based colorimetric sensors for degradation monitoring of various target foods

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The acid-base behaviour of dissolved organic matter in aquatic systems associated to Mero and Ebro rivers (Spain)

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The oceanic carbonate system governs the exchange of carbon between the atmosphere and the ocean serving as a significant, vast reservoir for CO₂ in both organic and inorganic forms at various depths. The intricate interplay of chemical, biological, and physical processes greatly influences the ocean's capacity to absorb and store atmospheric CO₂. Dissolved organic matter (DOM), a vital component of the carbonate system, functions as a dynamic carbon reservoir [1]. Beyond its role in atmospheric CO₂ storage, DOM supports ecosystems, impacts metal cycles essential for primary production and agriculture, and shapes the transport, behavior, and fate of environmental pollutants. DOM comprises a diverse array of structurally complex organic compounds, typically smaller than 0.2/0.7 μm. Variations in its chemical composition significantly affect its accumulation, fate, physicochemical characteristics, and binding properties. Despite its complexity, carboxylic acids and phenolic compounds represent key structural components of natural DOM [2, 3].

This research evaluated the physicochemical properties of DOM extracted from riverine and estuarine waters using potentiometric titrations. The proton-binding characteristics of DOM samples collected from the Mero and Ebro Rivers, located in northwest and northeast Spain respectively, were analyzed. Sampling sites (shown in Figure 1) were strategically selected to capture the evolution of DOM from the river sources to their oceanic outlets—the Atlantic Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea, respectively. Seasonal variations in DOM and associated parameters were studied across the selected sites. Additionally, the influence of ionic strength on DOM binding properties was assessed by fitting the data to the NICA-Donan model (Figure 2). The maximum number of carboxylic and phenolic groups found in samples taken from the Mero and the Ebro systems is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 1. Sampling sites in both Mero and Ebro systems

Figure 2. NICA-Donan master curve for acid-base equilibrium data in Mero river, Summer 2023.

Figure 3. DOM content of carboxylic and phenolic groups in Mero (left) and Ebro (right).

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Intercomparison Study of DGT Devices with Dihydroxamate-Based Binding Gels for Uranium(VI) Sampling in Freshwater

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Uranium is released into the environment through mining activities, production and use of nuclear fuel (~65 kt/year), reprocessing of spent fuel and storage of nuclear waste, coal burning, and spreading of phosphate fertilizers. Once discharged, uranium may migrate across various environmental compartments, ultimately leading to the contamination of trophic chains [1]. Monitoring such contamination, particularly in aquatic systems, calls for innovative analytical techniques capable of assessing both the distribution and bioavailability of actinides.

In that respect, Diffusive Gradients in Thin Films (DGT) is one of the most promising techniques for determining the concentration of labile metal species in aquatic environments, including wetlands and sediments [2]. Unfortunately, the most widely used and commercially available binding gels for uranium, namely the Chelex-100[®] ion-exchange resin and the TiO₂-based Metsorb[®] adsorbing material, are known to underperform in hard, carbonate-rich freshwater and seawater [3,4].

To overcome these shortcomings, we designed a pincer-like UO₂²⁺ chelator bearing two terminal hydroxamate bidentate groups able to coordinate the uranyl cation in its equatorial plane [5]. Potentiometric studies revealed a high binding affinity towards UO₂²⁺ and an excellent selectivity with respect to Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions. According to PHREEQC speciation

calculations, uranium(VI) is efficiently chelated between pH 4 and 8 even in the presence of major competing ions such as Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, and HCO₃⁻. Hence, the dihydroxamic acid was covalently grafted by amide bond formation onto a hydrophilic organic resin, Sephadex CM-25[®], and the resulting extracting material embedded in a binding gel made of agarose. The uranium(VI) uptake performances of the new DGT samplers made thereof were assessed under controlled laboratory conditions, using both mineral waters and synthetic seawater spiked with 20 µg/L of UO₂²⁺. Accordingly, uranium prevails as [M_xUO₂(CO₃)₃]^{(4-2x)-} triscarbonato species (M = Mg, x = 1; M = Ca, x = 0–2) in each medium. Results were benchmarked against commercial Chelex-100[®] and Metsorb[®] samplers, highlighting the superiority of the hydroxamic acid based extracting resin.

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Metal binding ability of tau (289-300) fragment

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Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the best known and most common form of neurodegenerative disorders, tauopathies. Its development is associated with the accumulation of amyloid- β plaques and hyperphosphorylated tau protein into neurofibrillary tangles [1, 2]. Different factors like oxidative stress, phosphorylation and dyshomeostatis causes the tau protein to dissociate from the microtubule and aggregate resulting in the formation of intracellular neurofibrillary tangles in a multistep process. It starts with the abnormal conformational changes and continues by dimerization or oligomerization with subsequent formation of neurofibrillary tangles [3, 4]. The dyshomeostasis of essential zinc, iron and copper may lead to the enhancement of free metal ions in neuron which results in conformational changes and consequent misfolding by binding of metal ions to the 2 cysteine or 12 histidine residues in the sequence, which are the most common metal binding amino acids in the tau protein [5].

Considering that Cys and His are the primary binding sites for metal ions, the tau fragment containing the potential donor groups Cys 291 and His 299 (tau 289-300; Ac-SKCGSKDNIKHN-NH₂) was investigated for their coordination and electrochemical behaviour. In addition to this, tau fragments containing only Cys 291, tau 288-293; Ac-QSKCGS-NH₂ and tau 289-292; Ac-SKCG-NH₂, as well as tau fragments containing only His 299; tau 292-301, Ac-GSKDNIKHVP-NH₂ and its asparagine mutant at position 300 were also synthesized and their coordination and electrochemical properties were investigated. The transition metal complexes of all these peptides were characterized to investigate their coordination mode, as these metal ions may be responsible for the aggregation of tau protein and thus may play role in the development of Alzheimer's disease.

The pH potentiometric titrations were performed for the above five ligands and their Ni(II) complexes. The stepwise deprotonation and coordination verified different complex formation over a pH range 3 to 11.

For Cys containing fragments (tau(289-292) and tau(288-293)), Ni(II) coordinates by the thiol group of cysteine and 2 deprotonated amide nitrogens at nearly the same pH resulting in the [NiLH] species. As the pH is increased, the third terminal amide nitrogen is deprotonated at a relatively higher pH to give [NiLH₂] complexes, where one coordination site of Ni²⁺ is saturated by the thiol group of Cys and three amide nitrogens, suggesting that the metal ion is bound in a complex with [N⁻,N⁻,N⁻,S⁻] coordination. The lysines are deprotonated at a higher pH but not coordinated to the metal ions.

In the study of Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes of the His containing ligands (tau(292-301)) a four-coordinated complex was observed as the major species, in which both metal ions are coordinated by the histidine imidazole N and 3 amide N. The UV-vis and circular dichroism spectroscopic studies of these complexes supported the results inferred from pH potentiometry that His 299 is a major binding

site in these tau fragments. The potentiometric and spectroscopic studies of the Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes of only His 299 fragment and its mutant concluded that the mutation of an uncoordinated amino acid like valine to asparagine in the fragment has little effect on the stability constant of complexes and no significant effect on the binding mode of metal ions to the tau fragment.

Comparative analysis of the stability constants calculated for all peptides and their Ni(II) complexes showed that, the peptides containing both His and Cys in the sequence are more stable than peptides containing only His, suggesting that if Cys is present in the sequence, it is involved in coordination with the metal ion.

The spectrophotometric and CD curves of Ni(II) complexes showed a clear shoulder peak characteristic of Ni-S binding in fragments containing cysteine, which was not observed in tau fragments containing histidine alone, indicating that Cys is a preferred binding site for Ni(II) in tau fragments 289-300 where both Cys and His are present in the sequence.

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Effect of Phosphorylation of Serine on the Complex Formation Process of Tau Protein Fragments

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The chemical interaction between metal ions and proteins, peptides are significant in the human body and it is important to get information about the processes occurring, which can be reversible like the coordination and phosphorylation, or irreversible ones which could also happen like the oxidative reactions or the hydrolytic processes [1].

Taupathies are one the major forms of neurodegenerative disorders, of which Alzheimer's disease is the best known and most common. It has a big association with the accumulation of hyperphosphorylated tau protein in the form of neurofibrillary tangles [2]. Tau protein plays an important role in the stabilization of microtubules of the nervous cell, and the interaction between metal ion and the protein fragments plays an important role in the accumulation process, but the exact mechanism of these accumulation processes still not satisfactorily clear [3].

The specific phosphorylation of Serine262 and Serine356 in tau protein by MARK kinase enzymes have been described to decrease the microtubule binding affinity of tau protein for microtubules, and the phosphorylation of this protein is associated with the destabilization of the tau microtubule complex and the assembly of tau protein into higher order aggregates and metal ions have a significant impact on this process [4,5].

In our work, we synthesized tau(262-270): Ac-STENLKHQP-NH₂ peptide by solid phase peptide synthesizer, we studied the coordination chemistry behaviour of this peptide with three metal ions [Cu(II), Ni(II) and Zn(II)] and also the loner peptide sequence tau(258-270) Ac-SKIGSTENLKHQP-NH₂. In order to clearly see the impact of phosorylation of serine on the complex formation process, we also studied the coordinatiation chemistry behaviour of these phosphorylated versions tau(258(P)-270) Ac-S(P)KIGSTENLKHQP-NH₂, tau(258-262(P)-270): Ac-SKIGS(P)TENLKHQP-NH₂, and hyperphosphorylated tau(258(P)-262(P)-270): Ac-S(P)KIGS(P)TENLKHQP-NH₂ with the same metal ions. The complex formation process of all peptides with these transition metal ions were thoroughly described. In case of all these peptides, histidyl resides are anchoring groups which are responsible for coordinating to the metal ion and further amide nitrogen atoms are also bond in the basic solution.

During solution equilibrium studies and different spectroscopic measurements, complex formation processes are investigated in the presence of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Zn(II) ions. We calculated the pK values of the ligands and the deprotonation constants, compositions of

the metal ion-peptides complexes by using PSEQUAD and SUPERQUAD software. By using the spectroscopic tools including UV-Vis, circular dichroism (CD) and EPR spectroscopy, we could confirm the coordination modes around metal ions and the structural geometry of the metal ion- peptide complex species at different pH values.

In this presentation will be shown how the phosphorylation of serine in different positions affects the stability and coordination of metal complexes of peptides.

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Effect of threonine on the interaction between transition metal ions and tau protein fragments

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Neurodegenerative tauopathies are characterized by extracellular protein deposits of amyloid- β and intracellular aggregates of hyperphosphorylated tau in the brain. Great number of publications supports that otherwise essential metal ions (such as zinc and copper) play an important role in the development of neurodegeneration. The histidine imidazole nitrogen donor atoms are frequent metal binding sites in proteins and tau is relatively rich in this moiety. The 12 histidyl residues of the protein are well-separated and can be found in different chemical environment, hence we can assume that their metal binding properties – at least slightly – differ. [1-3]

On the other hand, the tau protein contains a large number of serine and threonine amino acids, the phosphorylation of which results in a hyperphosphorylated protein that can promote protein aggregation.[4] In addition, the position of the serine and threonine amino acids relative to histidine may also influence the processes that occur in the presence of metal ions. It is known that peptides containing the –TXH– or –SXH– sequence induce hydrolytic processes in the presence of Ni(II) in alkaline media, which may lead to abnormal protein function.[5-7]

In the tau protein, threonine amino acids are also found in the histidine environment and in the histidine 32 and 388 are in the –TXH– environment. This also has impact for the stability and spectral parameters of the Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes of the peptides mimicking this two histidines environment.[8-9] Thus, a systematic study of the metal complexes of oligopeptides and their mutants containing this sequence was performed completed with the peptide fragment containing a –TH– segment. Our aim was to understand the role of threonine in more detail.

In addition to the previously studied Tau(26-33) peptide containing the –TXH– segment, mutant peptides of the Tau(29-34) fragment (-YTMHQD-) were synthesized: Tau(Y29A-34) (Ac-ATMHQD-NH₂), Tau(Y29A-M31A-34) (Ac-ATAHQD-NH₂) and Tau(Y29A-T30A-34) (Ac-AAMHQD-NH₂). The Tau(385-390) (Ac-KTDHGA-NH₂) peptide also contains a –TXH– sequence, while in the Tau(371-376) (Ac-IETKHL-NH₂) fragment threonine and histidine are in adjacent position.

The studies showed that peptides containing the –TXH– sequence form complexes with both Cu(II) and Ni(II) ions have similar stoichiometries and structure as other peptides containing one histidine. The presence of threonine, however, increases the stability of the formed complexes and the metal ion-induced amide nitrogen deprotonation occurs at lower pH.

In the presence of Ni(II), hydrolytic processes are already induced around pH 8, but detectable changes are only observed over a longer time period. So the characterization of complex forming processes are reliable. In alkaline media, however, the hydrolytic processes are considerably faster. At the same time, in the presence of Cu(II) at 25 °C, even in a strongly alkaline medium, no other process is observed that occurs in parallel with complex formation.

Our studies have also shown that these processes clearly occur in the presence of threonine one amino acid away from histidine, while for peptide containing the -TH- segment and for peptide without threonine, only complex formation processes similar to those of other peptides were detected.

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Coordination Chemistry of Transition Metal Ions with a Macrocyclic Pyridinic Ligand Containing Mixed N/S Donor Atoms.

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Oxidative stress, resulting from an imbalance in the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), is closely associated with several pathologies, including neurodegenerative diseases, inflammatory diseases and cancer. [1] In the research for new therapeutic strategies, metal complexes derived from macrocyclic ligands have shown great potential due to their ability to intervene in redox processes. [2]

The central aim of this study is the synthesis and coordination chemistry of a macrocyclic ligand that combines secondary amino groups and thioethers as donor atoms in its structure. [3] Its coordination with metal ions of biological interest, such as Cu(II), Mn(II) and Fe(II), leads to the formation of complexes with the ideal structural and electronic properties to interact with ROS.

Figure 1: Complex structure of the ligand studied with copper.

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Self-Assembled Hydrolytic Metallocages with Heterocyclic Diamines

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Open-chain polyamine ligands functionalized with heterocyclic rings, such as pyridine, represent a class of compounds of great interest in the field of coordination and supramolecular chemistry. The chemical structure of these ligands is characterized by a combination of flexibility and high nucleophilicity in the amino groups, and structural rigidity and aromatic character in the pyridine ring. This provides an optimal balance between adaptability and geometric control that can be used to build up supramolecular ensembles. Moreover, the position of the nitrogen atom should directly influence the final geometry and structural organization of the complex. [1,2]

The present study deals with the coordination chemistry of the Cu²⁺ with a series of pyridine-functionalized methylated diamines. We evaluate the influence of varying substitution position of the pyridine on the structure and reactivity of the complexes formed. [3]

Whereas the structure of the 2-substituted pyridine diamine provides discrete monomeric complexes in which both the amine and pyridine coordinate the same metal ion, the 3- substituted pyridine gives rise to an amazing hydrolytic metallocage involving ten copper ions and eight ligands. The copper ions coordinated by the secondary amines are held together by dihydroxo bridges, while the remaining two copper ions are coordinated by the pyridine rings. Interestingly enough the formation of the cages is reproducible highlighting the key role of the pyridine substitution.

Figure 1: Front and top view of the metallocage

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Method development of a simple digestion method for plant samples with applications in copper phytoremediation studies

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Viticulture is the science of grapevine cultivation and plays an important role in wine production and quality. One of the main factors that directly affects the quality of this crop is mildew, a fungal disease caused by the pathogen *Plasmopara viticola*, which primarily damages the leaves of vines. One of the most well-known fungicides used to combat this disease is Bordeaux mixture, discovered in 1882. It is composed of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, and its discovery has promoted the continued use of copper-based agents in viticulture such as copper oxychloride.

There is growing concern about copper (Cu) accumulation in soils. Although it is an essential micronutrient for plants, at high concentrations it becomes highly toxic, inhibiting root growth, disrupting photosynthesis, and reducing dry mass production, among other detrimental effects [1].

To mitigate this dangerous accumulation over the years and to avoid more aggressive remediation techniques (e.g., soil pH modification, physical extraction), phytoremediation has been studied as a sustainable alternative. This approach takes advantage of the ability of certain plants species to hyperaccumulate Cu in their tissues, thereby gradually reducing soil contamination.

It has been demonstrated that *Plantago lanceolata* (commonly known as ribwort plantain) can accumulate more than 100 $\mu\text{g/g}$ of Cu, whereas the normal concentration in plants ranges from 5–20 $\mu\text{g/g}$. This property, along with the fact that it is a native Mediterranean species frequently found in vineyards, makes *Plantago lanceolata* a promising candidate for Cu recovery [2, 3].

Wild *Plantago lanceolata* specimens were collected, thoroughly washed, and dried at 60°C until reaching constant weight. Roots and leaves were ground and acid-digested using both microwave and Hot Block methods for comparison. Total Cu content was then analyzed using Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS). An acid digestion method using a Hot Block has been developed and validated as an alternative to microwave-assisted digestion for sample preparation, ensuring complete digestion of plant tissues while reducing operational complexity and cost. The optimized method was validated using a Certified Reference Material (CRM).

Subsequently, *Plantago lanceolata* seeds were cultivated under controlled laboratory conditions and exposed to different Cu concentrations, both in a hydroponic nutrient solution

and in a universal substrate to simulate real-world conditions as closely as possible, as a preliminary step prior to experiments using vineyard soil.

To complement the analysis of total metal uptake and accumulation in roots and leaves, a study of Cu speciation is planned across different plant tissues. Later, various strategies will be explored to increase the copper-extraction capacity of *Plantago lanceolata* (assisted phytoremediation).

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Solution chemistry, molecular recognition, life and biodiversity, seen by the eyes of a child from the Moon!

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To those who contributed to the development of Biological Inorganic Chemistry

Based on the simplified idea that matter and light are two sides of the same coin, after the Big Bang, the Earth appeared as part of the Universe in the form of a large drop of molten mass. Its progressive cooling was accompanied by the complete consumption of atmospheric O₂, producing water in the oceans as well as many of the minerals in the Earth's crust. Under these conditions, abiogenesis was overcome in an oxygen-free atmosphere! But... when, where and how did life arise? (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Scheme of the origin of life and the subsequent evolution.

When: Under a favourable set of circumstances, by means of 'molecular recognition' between suitable chemicals, through abiogenesis. **Where:** Around hot springs that provided the necessary energy. **How:** Life appeared in solution (chemistry)! The great leap from abiogenesis to living organisms occurs when conventional chemical equilibria give rise to biological systems that are far from conventional equilibria. In such cases, one of many possible processes emerges that is enzymatically favoured by a catalyst. Under these conditions, some cyanobacteria develop anoxygenic photosynthesis, which uses H₂S and leaves S as a by-product. A tremendous optimisation leads to oxygenic photosynthesis, which leaves O₂ as a by-product, condemning anaerobic organisms to extinction (Figure 2). Both photosyntheses coexisted for ~0.1 eons (eon = 10⁹ years).

Figure 2. Anoxygenic and oxygenic photosynthesis.

The increasing presence of O₂ alters the bioavailability of essential elements, immobilising Fe(II) as Fe(III) and mobilising Cu(I) as Cu(II), but does not affect Zn(II), soft Pearson's acid, without redox chemistry. Zn fingers (ZF) control (among other things) the 'first step of gene expression', with the exception of some diatoms, using Cd(II) instead. The earliest ZFs have Zn(II) bound to four S-thiolate-Cys donors, soft Pearson's bases! S-Cys is gradually replaced by N-His donors (borderline Pearson's bases). Natural ZF are known with one, two or three S-Cys replaced by N-His, but not by four N-His! Although 'artificial Zn(N-His)₄ fingers' have been reported [1]. Clear evidence of the evolution towards biodiversity that guarantees both life and its extinction. Similarly, natural Zn-porphyrins do not play a relevant role, but synthetic Zn-porphyrins are used as catalysts [2].

Concluding remarks: Survival of living organisms requires the combination of two things: The ability to reproduce and adapt to the environment. In a nutshell: 'I am me and my circumstances, and if I don't save them, I won't save myself'. One question remains unanswered! Could another metal ion, such as Zn(II), be responsible for controlling the first and subsequent peaks in gene expression? Well... we don't know! But ... '*Impossible n'est pas français*'.

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Interaction between novel, ambidentate hydroxy-pyridinone derivatives and platinum group metal ions

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Hypoxia has features to play important role in tumors cells. Due to this feature, the hypoxia-activated prodrugs are compounds designed to target selectively tumor cells. These compounds can be releasing cytotoxic agents by reduction of cobalt(III) complexes to Co(II) oxidation state in low-oxygen environments. Therefore, these complexes can be designed to form labile Co(II) species, resulting in hypoxia-selective anticancer activity [1]. Platinum (Pt) anticancer drugs have been used to treat various cancers. However, they have a poor selectivity and high toxicity towards normal cells and an increasing chemoresistance. Therefore, the researchers have been searching for novel metallo-anticancers with Pt group metals.

During our work recently we have synthesized novel, ambidentate ligands using different amino acids such as Me-Cys-Fmoc-OH, Met-Fmoc-OH, Bn-Cys-Fmoc-OH and Fmoc-His(Triyl)-OH) and a hydroxy-pyridinone unit connecting them a chain of different length. While the amino acid part can provide with an (N,S) or (N,N) chelate for the platinum group metal, the pyridinone entity can bind the Co(III) ion. The synthesized ligands were characterized using a variety of analytical techniques, including pH-potentiometric equilibrium studies in solution, NMR, and MS. We have also carried out potentiometric titrations with organorhodium and –ruthenium ions to explore the metal binding capabilities of the ligands and the donor atom preference of the metal ions. These results can provide useful information for the planned synthesis of the heterobimetallic complexes in the solid state. This contribution will summarize our recent results in this field. b.

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Palladium nanoparticles supported on non-covalently functionalized graphene nanoplatelets: Preparation, characterization and study of their catalytic properties

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Metal nanoparticles (MNPs) have attracted great interest due to their unique properties such as enhanced catalytic activity, high surface to volume ratio and optical properties, which make them excellent candidates to different applications in diverse scientific and technological areas such as biomedicine, environmental remediation and catalysis. Immobilization of MNPs onto different supports is a widely used strategy to prevent their aggregation and improve their catalytic properties [1]. Due to their chemical inertness, high surface area and potential for surface functionalization, in recent years, graphene derivatives have attracted significant interest as supports for MNPs [2]. Since functionalization of graphene surfaces not only improves their dispersibility but also their affinity toward metal species, the introduction of appropriate surface functionalities can greatly favor the immobilization of MNPs on graphene surfaces. Furthermore, a homogeneous distribution of surface functionalities will also determine a homogeneous distribution of MNPs.

Here we present our results on the preparation, characterization and study of catalytic properties of a new material consisting of palladium nanoparticles (PdNPs) supported on non-covalently functionalized graphene nanoplatelets. The material has been obtained by a sustainable and facile synthetic method which draws on the positive influence of the metal complexing properties of the surface chemical functions of graphene nanoplatelets (GNP) to achieve metal NPs. This method consists of several steps: 1) non-covalent functionalization of GNP surface based on the attachment of 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) molecules on the arene centres of low-functionalized GNP, *via* irreversible π -stacking interactions; 2) binding of controlled amounts of Pd(II) ions on the functionalized GNP, through the formation of Pd(II)-complexes by the phenanthroline surface functions; 3) Pd(II) reduction to form Pd(0) NPs homogeneously distributed on the GNP surface, giving rise to GNP-Phen-PdNPs materials. It is worth noting the dual role played by the surface functions of GNP in the formation of PdNPs: on the one hand, they coordinate to the Pd(II) ions, improving the Pd(II) adsorption capacity of the support and leading to a homogeneous distribution of Pd(II) ions on the GNP surface; and on the other hand, after Pd(II) reduction, they stabilize the Pd(0) NPs by complexing the zerovalent atoms of the nanoparticles.

The obtained palladium-decorated graphene nanoplatelets have been characterized by XPS, XRD and HRTEM and their catalytic properties have been studied in the reductive

degradation reaction of rhodamine B (RhB), considered one of the most important pollutants in effluents from the textile, leather, cosmetics, wood and paper industries. The progress of RhB degradation has been followed by means of UV-Vis absorption spectrophotometry (Figure 1). The study shows a remarkable catalytic activity of GNP-Phen-PdNPs, which clearly improves with increasing amounts of PdNPs. These promising results encourage the search for new catalysts based on MNPs for the degradation of dyes in wastewater.

Figure 1. Time-dependent UV–vis spectral changes recorded for NaBH₄-induced reduction of rhodamine B (RhB): a) uncatalyzed, b) catalyzed by GNP-Phen-PdNPs.

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Thermodynamic and spectroscopic analysis of peptide-based enzyme mimics containing the ATCUN site

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Enzyme mimics (EMs) are molecular entities that typically replicate the binding and catalytic function of natural enzymes [1]. In this work we focus on peptide-based EMs with an ATCUN (Amino-Terminal Copper and Nickel) binding site, in order to promote a multitarget antimicrobial mechanism. Our approach in designing novel EMs relies on synthetic branched peptides to generate a previously unexplored category of EMs. A biocompatible central scaffold serves as the core of the EM structure, to which various oligopeptides can be attached [2,3]. The presented work consists of a preliminary study of two selected oligopeptides: AAHAWG-NH₂ and AAHAWGELLKLLLEELKG-NH₂. The peptide ability to form stable Cu(II) complexes has been investigated, together with the ability to generate reactive oxygen species. Indeed, the presence of an ATCUN motif can lead to an increased antimicrobial power, due to copper catalytic action. Potentiometric titrations, mass spectrometry and different spectroscopic techniques (e.g. UV-Vis absorption, circular dichroism) have been employed to thoroughly study the metal interaction with the selected peptides (Figure 1).

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Figure 1. Coordination hypothesis for the Cu(II)/AAHAWGELLKLLLEELKG-NH₂ complex.

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Effect of enantiomeric modification on the coordination and antimicrobial properties of Clavanin C

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Antibiotic resistance is an escalating global concern, posing a serious threat to public health. According to projections by the World Health Organization (WHO), multidrug-resistant bacterial infections could be responsible for up to 10 million deaths annually by the year 2050. Among the most promising alternatives to conventional antibiotics are antimicrobial peptides (AMPs), which exhibit strong and broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity [1].

The coordination of divalent metal ions can significantly enhance the antimicrobial properties of AMPs. For example, clavanin C - a marine AMP isolated from *Styela clava* - forms complexes with Cu(II) and Zn(II) ions that exhibit remarkable activity against pathogens[2]. However, the use of AMPs is often limited due to their low enzymatic stability.

One possible strategy to increase peptide resistance to enzymatic degradation is enantiomeric exchange modification of the native peptide. An especially innovative approach in the bioinorganic chemistry of AMPs is the retro-inverso strategy. This method involves not only enantiomeric exchange but also reversing the peptide sequence (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Sequences of investigated peptides: A) native clavanin C, B) D-clavanin C and C) Retro-Inverso Clavanin C.

Potentiometric titration, mass spectrometry and spectroscopic methods (UV-Vis, CD and Far-UV CD) allowed us to determine coordination spheres of modified clavanins complexes and

learn their secondary structures. We also used the HPLC method to evaluate the effect of enantiomeric exchange on enzymatic stability of peptides.

This study aimed to investigate the coordination behavior and antimicrobial properties of structurally modified clavamin C peptides. Furthermore, we evaluated the impact of enantiomeric exchange strategies - specifically D-amino acid substitution and the retro-inverso approach - on the enzymatic stability of clavamin C.

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Histatins in action: exploring the relationship between coordination chemistry, stability and antimicrobial activity of salivary peptides

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Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) constitute a crucial component of the innate immune defense across diverse organisms. These small, cationic peptides - typically composed of fewer than 100 amino acid residues - contribute to host protection by exhibiting direct microbicidal activity or by inhibiting microbial proliferation. AMPs have garnered increasing interest as promising therapeutic candidates, particularly due to their enhanced antimicrobial efficacy upon interaction with metal ions. Such interactions can impair microbial viability and pathogenicity through metal ion sequestration, a mechanism referred to as "nutritional immunity." Additionally, coordination with metal ions can modulate the physicochemical properties of AMPs, including their net charge and secondary structure, further potentiating their antimicrobial function.[1] Saliva represents a rich source of AMPs, notably histatins, which display pronounced activity against fungal pathogens such as *Candida albicans* and bacterial species, including members of the clinically relevant ESKAPE group.[2]

We investigated the correlation between coordination chemistry and the antimicrobial properties of Cu(II) and Zn(II) complexes of histatins, employing a comprehensive set of analytical techniques including potentiometric titration, UV-Vis spectroscopy, circular dichroism (CD), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) and antimicrobial activity assays. Cu(II) ions typically coordinate in a binding mode analogous to that observed in albumin, with the exception of histatin 4, which lacks the ATCUN binding motif. In contrast, Zn(II) exhibits coordination versatility, interacting either with the carboxylate group of glutamic acid and two histidine imidazole rings or with two histidyl residues, indicative of presence of polymorphic binding sites. The antimicrobial efficacy of both free histatins and their metal complexes is strongly pH-dependent, with Zn(II) coordination generally enhancing antimicrobial activity. Furthermore, the antimicrobial activity of both the metal complexes and the free ligands is markedly greater against Gram-positive bacterial species than against Gram-negative ones. Moreover, binding of Zn(II)

to histatin 3–4 and histatin 5–8 induces notable conformational changes, promoting increased α -helical content.[3,4]

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Unusual Chaperonins of Pathogenic Mycobacteria: Correlation between Coordination Chemistry, Structure, Dynamics, and Biology

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Antimicrobial resistance (AR) represents a major global public health threat, directly causing at least 1.27 million deaths worldwide in 2019 and contributing to nearly 5 million fatalities. [1] The growing inefficacy of conventional antibiotic therapies has driven researchers to explore alternative antimicrobial strategies, among which the antibacterial properties of metals have gained significant attention.

The *Mycobacterium* genus comprises several clinically significant pathogens - such as *M. tuberculosis*, *M. smegmatis*, *M. bovis*, and *M. leprae* - which have substantial impacts on both human health and animal husbandry. In particular, attention has been drawn to the GroEL1 chaperonins found in non-tuberculous mycobacteria. These proteins are pivotal in ensuring the proper folding of other polypeptides into their most energetically favourable conformations. Notably, GroEL1 chaperonins possess a histidine-rich C-terminal tail (HRCT), and the histidine residues within this domain are adept at binding metal ions. [2, 3] Recent studies suggest that GroEL1 chaperonins play a crucial role in metabolic and energetic adaptation under cellular stress conditions. Furthermore, these proteins have emerged as promising molecular targets for novel antibacterial therapies, leveraging the antimicrobial properties of metal ions. [4] Two key mechanisms underlie this approach: the toxic concentration of metal ions and nutrient immunity. [5, 6]

To develop new drugs, it is imperative to conduct thorough investigations into the properties of complexes formed between potential virulence factors and drugs - complexes of copper ions Cu(II) and other divalent metal cations M(II) with the GroEL1 HRCT motifs. This entails characterising the pH-dependent thermodynamics of HRCT-M(II) interactions, elucidating the structural and dynamic properties of M(II)-GroEL1 complexes, and conducting *in vivo* experiments to assess the impact of GroEL1 deletion on bacterial survival under various environmental conditions. These comprehensive investigations are expected to yield a detailed understanding of the metal ion-dependent machinery of GroEL1 in mycobacteria, potentially paving the way for innovative antibacterial strategies.

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Engineering peptide inhibitors to target zinc-dependent bacterial metalloproteinases

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Figure 1: Mechanism of inhibition by a substrate-mimicking inhibitor. The inhibitor binds to the active site via a zinc-binding group (ZBG), preventing substrate cleavage and release [1].

With antibiotic resistance on the rise, once-treatable infections are becoming deadly. As traditional treatments fail, new therapeutic strategies are urgently needed [2]. Among bacterial virulence factors, metalloproteinases (MPs) from the M4 and M10 families play critical roles in host tissue degradation and immune evasion. Their activity depends on Zn(II) coordination in the active site, making zinc an essential cofactor and a potential target for inhibition [3].

In our study, we investigated several active sites of MPs from M4 and M10 families from antibiotic-resistant strains, focusing on the coordination chemistry of their active sites with Zn(II) and Cu(II). We compared the binding properties of these metals, exploring the potential for copper to displace zinc and thereby inhibit enzyme activity. Additionally, we performed point mutations to identify key amino acids that are most important for metal coordination [4]. Furthermore, we designed substrate-based peptide inhibitors that mimic the enzymes' natural substrates, which offer enhanced selectivity and improved pharmacological profiles compared to traditional inhibitors (Fig. 1) [5]. We also examined how these inhibitors coordinate with metal ions and interact with the active sites.

Comprehensive biophysical analyses including mass spectrometry, NMR spectroscopy, UV–Vis spectroscopy, and circular dichroism provided valuable insights into the differential binding properties of zinc and copper, as well as the interactions among the metal ions, active sites, and inhibitors.

By unraveling the intricate metal coordination of bacterial metalloproteinases, we open new doors for designing precision-targeted inhibitors. Our findings pave the way for disrupting bacterial resilience at its core offering a fresh avenue in the fight against antibiotic resistance.

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Selected silver(I) complexes: aqueous speciation, structural features, stability and bioevaluation

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Silver has been used for centuries for its antimicrobial properties, and its modern therapeutic potential has re-emerged with the development of silver-based complexes as alternatives to traditional antibiotics [1]. Among the possible oxidation states, silver(I) is the most stable and biologically relevant, forming a wide variety of coordination compounds with nitrogen-, sulfur-, and oxygen-donor ligands. The coordination behavior of Ag(I) is governed by its closed-shell d^{10} configuration, resulting in geometries, predominantly linear but also trigonal planar, or distorted tetrahedral depending on the ligand environment.

Aqueous speciation is particularly important in bioinorganic chemistry, where pH-dependent equilibria, hydrolysis, and ligand exchange processes influence both the therapeutic potential and toxicity profile of metal complexes [2].

Despite extensive interest in silver chemistry, the solution behavior and speciation of Ag(I) complexes in aqueous environments—where biological interactions occur—are still not fully explored.

This contribution provides insights into the aqueous speciation and stability of selected silver(I) complexes with biologically relevant ligands (amino acids and peptides). A combination of potentiometry, NMR spectroscopy, and theoretical techniques were used to characterize the ligands' complexing and structural properties in the Ag(I)-selected ligands systems in the aqueous solution. In addition, biological evaluation assays, including

antibacterial and cytotoxic testing, were used to assess the relationship between solution chemistry and biological performance.

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Adding fluorescent properties to Malten: coordination and preliminary biological studies on two fluorescent derivatives

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In the last two decades the group of Urbino has focused its efforts on the design and synthesis of bis-maltol polyamines ligands. In particular, *Malten* (**L1** in Fig. 1, N,N'-bis[(3-hydroxy-4-pyron-2-yl)methyl]-N,N'-dimethylethylenediamine), a small molecule that contains two maltol units linked to a N,N-dimethylethylenediamine scaffold, is one of the most promising in terms of both antineoplastic and coordination properties [1-4]. Indeed **L1**, on one hand, can be preorganized by Cu(II) to become a suitable metallo-receptor for hard cations such as Rare Earth ions in aqueous solution. On the other hand, this ligand was analyzed at both biological and molecular levels for its antiproliferative activity against cancer cells showing biological activities associated with the modulation of genes having key roles in cell cycle progression and apoptosis.

In order to preserve the same molecular coordination framework of **L1** but adding fluorescent properties to the system, recently the two ligands **L2** and **L3** (Fig. 1) have been synthesized. In **L2**, the two maltol units of *Malten* have been replaced by two 3-hydroxy-4-chromone moieties analogously linked to the same polyamine unit [5], while in **L3** an anthranilic group attached to the ethylenediamine moiety has been added.

As in the case of **L1**, we searched for the suitable transition metal ion able to preorganize **L2** and **L3**, forcing the four 3-hydroxychromone (**L2**) and maltol units (**L3**) oxygen atoms to converge and form a negative pocket maintaining the fluorescence properties of the systems. Interesting results were obtained for the two fluorescent ligands, that shown different behaviors depending on the metal ion considered.

In addition, with the aim of observing how the structural changes made to the system may affect the biological activity, the two new ligands are being evaluated in comparison to **L1** for their ability to reduce cell survival of cancer cells.

Figure 1: Molecular structures of Malten (L1) and its fluorescent derivatives L2 and L3

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Interaction of salane-type compounds with transition metal ions

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N₂O₂-type ligands play an important role in the development of modern coordination chemistry and in the production of new metal complex catalysts. They also have important applications in pharmaceutical chemistry. Their derivatives are also increasingly used in medicinal chemistry, as they have been reported to have anti-tumour and cytotoxic effects, and thus have potential for use in in vitro and in vivo studies. Our aim was to synthesize new water-soluble salane-type N₂O₂ donor ligands (sulfosalane) and study their interaction with different transition metal ions (copper(II), nickel(II) and zinc(II)) including coordination and oxidation. [1, 2]

Their protective effect against metal ion-catalysed oxidation of peptides was also studied. We have investigated the relationship between structure and stability of metal complexes; how the increasing size of the bridge between donor atoms affects the metal ion binding ability and the protection of peptides against metal ion-catalysed oxidation. For our studies, we used pH-potentiometry, UV-

Scheme: Structure of the studied salane-type compounds, x = 1: HSS, x = 2: PrHSS, x = 3: BuHSS, x = 4: PentHSS, x = 5: HexHSS

Our studies have shown that increasing the size of the bridge between donor atoms typically increases the basicity of ligands, but is not associated with an increase in metal ion binding capacity. For none of the transition metal ions studied does this factor favour metal ion binding, but for Cu(II) ions it allows multiple metal ions to coordinate to a single ligand or to form complexes with dimeric structures.

The protective effect of the compounds against peptide oxidation was studied for a human prion protein fragment (HuPrP(103-112)) using the Cu(II)/H₂O₂ system. The progress of oxidation was monitored by HPLC. The ligands tested hinder the metal ion-catalysed oxidation of the peptide. It was found that this protective effect is more effective when the coordination sphere of the Cu(II) ion is saturated, which may be the case with shorter connecting bridges between donor atoms.

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Fluorescent imprinted polymers: promising probes for fluoride sensing in water

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Fluoride anion is widely distributed in the Earth’s crust and natural waters. It is an example of a double-edged sword, producing both beneficial and harmful health effects depending on its concentration [1]. This highlights the need for new low-cost and portable sensors capable of *in situ* monitoring of F⁻ ions. Unfortunately, achieving high levels of water compatibility and fluoride specificity remains a challenge. In this study, six new urea-based compounds were prepared and evaluated as fluoride sensors in water (**A1-A6**; Figure 1).

Figure 1. Discrete urea-based sensors prepared in this work.

Sensors **A1**, **A3** and **A6** were found to be fluorescent in water, with **A1** and **A6** being particularly sensitive and selective to fluoride (Table 1). Unfortunately, both sensors exhibit cross-sensitivity to Cl⁻ (**A6**) and H₂PO₄⁻ (**A1**). To improve performance, the discrete probes were embedded into a fluoride-imprinted polymeric matrix, to give solid-state sensors **A1P**, **A3P** and **A6P**. Of these, only **A1P** demonstrated satisfactory performance, achieving a sensitivity of 360 M⁻¹, a low detection limit (35 μM), and a linear response range (118–6300 μM) that encompasses the United States Environmental Protection Agency fluoride limit (211 μM), along with excellent anion specificity (Table 1, Figure 2a). Furthermore, **A1P** was

monitored along a cycling test, displaying good reusability (Figure 2b). Moreover, the application of **A1P** to a real sample analysis (mouthwash) gave excellent results, with an average recovery level of $102 \pm 2\%$, constituting the first example of a low-cost anion-imprinted polymeric probe tailored for the selective sensing of fluoride in aqueous samples. We are now assembling the best-performing polymers into sandwich-type multilayer devices compatible with portable fluoride monitoring systems. The first results are promising, showing a significant enhancement in the sensitivity, selectivity, and detection limits compared to the discrete and polymeric probes.

Table 1. Sensitivity quantified by the Stern-Volmer constant (K_{SV}) and detection limit (LD) for some of the discrete and polymeric sensors in water.

8,5	A1		A1P		A3		A3P		A6		A6P	
	K_{SV} (M^{-1})	LD (μM)	K_{SV} (M^{-1})	LD (μM)	K_{SV} (M^{-1})	LD (μM)	K_{SV} (M^{-1})	LD (μM)	K_{SV} (M^{-1})	LD (μM)	K_{SV} (M^{-1})	LD (μM)
F ⁻	871(50)	8	360(13)	35	37(2)	192	9.8(4)	1796	11856(453)	0.7	9.9(1)	1654
Cl ⁻	22(1)		4.5(2)		393(2) 23(2)		6.2(2)		11115(893)			
Br ⁻	20(1)		8.2(4)		433(23) 57(3)		6.4(4)		298(23)			
I ⁻	111(2)		8.6(3)		640(33) 90(3)		6.9(3)		2574(191)			
NO ₃ ⁻	14.9(8)		---		60(3)		19.0(3)		---			
H ₂ PO ₄ ⁻	1616(79)		8.3(3)		100(4)		6.3(3)		1082(42)			

Figure 2. a) Optical sensitivity of **A1P-NIP**, **A1P**, **A3P** and **A6P**. Also shown: **A1P** on a paper strip under UV light, with and without water or fluoride solution (6 mM). b) Optical response of **A1P** in cyclic testing, with alternating fluoride exposure, centrifugation, and methanol washing.

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Xanthurenic Acid as a Metal Ligand: Insights from Comparative Analysis of Tryptophan-Derived Metabolites

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Xanthurenic acid (XA), is a natural compound and a well-known metabolite from tryptophan kynurenine pathway, acting as an ionophore (i.e, it is able to transport particular ions, as metal cations, by reversible binding, across the lipid membrane of cells) [1]. As such, understanding XA's role in biological systems relative to its metal ion interactions is crucial for exploring its potential in therapeutic contexts, particularly concerning metabolic disorders. Nevertheless, despite its potential relation with neurodegenerative diseases due to its ROS scavenging ability and Fe³⁺ complex formation [2], a complete understanding of its chemical speciation is still lacking. As such, we present herein the study of the binding ability of XA towards the trivalent metal cations Fe³⁺ and Ga³⁺, and the divalents Cu²⁺ and Zn²⁺. Each XA/M system was investigated individually, in KCl_(aq) at $I = 0.2 \text{ mol} \cdot \text{dm}^{-3}$ and $T = 298.15 \text{ K}$, by UV-Vis spectrophotometric titrations.

The results obtained indicate the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 metal-to-ligand species with different protonation states, in all studied systems (i.e. M(XA)H_x and M(XA)₂H_x). Based on the stoichiometry of the formed complex and on its structural similarities with 8-HQA, is not surprising that hydroxyl group in 4

Experimental UV-Vis spectra of Fe³⁺/XA system vs. pH ($c_{\text{XA}} = 3 \times c_{\text{Fe}} = 1.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$)

position is not being involved in complexation and, thus, remaining in its protonated form even during complex formation. The relative stabilities of formed metal complexes were compared with those formed by its congener structures, i.e., 8-HQA [3,4] and Kynurenic acid (KynA), in terms of the influence of the presence of different hydroxyl groups in several positions on its activity.

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Modelling the solubility and the acid-base properties of 3,4-pyridinedicarboxylic in aqueous media and binding ability towards some metal cations

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Cinchomeric acid (3,4-pyridinedicarboxylic acid, CA) is one of the six isomers of pyridine carboxylic acid [1]. Generally, pyridine carboxylic acids act as chelating agents for elements such as chromium, zinc, manganese, copper, iron, and molybdenum in the body. They are also used as intermediates in the production of pharmaceuticals and metal salts for applications as nutritional supplements. Metal complexes with biologically important ligands are often more effective than the free ligands themselves. Despite its significance, few studies have been reported in the literature regarding the thermodynamic properties of CA, such as its acid–base behavior, solubility, and interactions with biologically and environmentally relevant metal cations. Therefore, in this study, we report as results the values of the protonation constants of CA in various ionic media (NaCl_(aq), KCl_(aq), Et₄NI_(aq), NaClO₄_(aq)) ionic strengths ($0.1 \leq I/\text{mol kg}^{-1} \leq 1$), and temperature ($T =$ from 283.15 to 318.15 K). Additionally, stability constants for complexes of CA with different metal cations M^{n+} (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , La^{3+}) were determined by potentiometric titrations at different ionic strengths in KCl ($0.1 \leq I/\text{mol L}^{-1} \leq 1$) at $T = 298.15$ K. The dependence of the protonation and stability constants on ionic strength and temperature was analyzed using both a Debye–Hückel-type equation and the Specific Ion Interaction Theory (SIT) approach. Differences in the $\log K_i^H$ values obtained across the three ionic media were interpreted in terms of the formation of weak complexes between CA and the cations of the supporting electrolytes. To gain a more comprehensive understanding of its thermodynamic behavior, the total solubility and the solubility of the neutral species of CA were determined in NaCl_(aq) and KCl_(aq) (by UV spectrophotometry) and Et₄NI (by potentiometry) at 298.15 K at various ionic strengths. Setschenow coefficients and activity coefficients of the neutral species were also computed.

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Complex forming capabilities of ambidentate hydroxy-pyridinone derivatives bearing N-heteroaromatic ring

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Poorly developed vascular networks in tumour tissues result in lower oxygen concentrations compared to healthy cells offering a promising target for drugs with high selectivity. The hypoxic environment in malignant cell growth may promote the selective reduction of inert Co(III) complexes with sufficient redox potential, leading to the release of bioactive ligand. If the ligand to be complexed has ambidentate properties, it may also be suitable for the binding of a second metal ion, which has been shown to have anticancer activity [1].

The appropriate redox potential in Co(III) complexes can be set up with ligands containing a 4N+2O donor atom set. Previous research indicated that the redox and complexation properties of the complexes can be fine-tuned by changing the aromatic or aliphatic nature of the ligand containing the 4N donor atom and the functionality of the ligand containing the 2O donor atom [2-4].

In our work, we aimed at the synthesis of novel, ambidentate hydroxy-pyridinone conjugates and a more detailed study of metal ion binding of them. During the synthesis, we have modified the coordinating end of the ambidentate ligands (N,N). Thus, a containing pyridine, pyrrole, imidazole or quinoline heteroaromatic ring containing ligands were prepared and the effect of the position of the N-donor atom on complex formation (formation of a 5- or 6-membered chelate) was studied [5]. Furthermore, we have also made modifications to the length of the aliphatic chain connecting the hydroxypyridinone and the heteroaromatic ring and investigated how this affects their interaction with $[(\eta^5\text{-Cp}^*)\text{Rh}]^{2+}$ or $[(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cym})\text{Ru}]^{2+}$ ions.

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